

Agro2Circular

D1.7 – Energy and Water Recommendations

November 2023

Authors: Victor Fabregat (REG); Clara Navarro (REG); Juana María Pagán Carpe (REG); David Campos Peñalver (REG); Janneke Dickhout (CEW); Jordi Moreno (CEW);

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Technical references

Project Acronym	Agro2Circular
Project Title	TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR
Project Coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó CETEC fuensanta.monzo@agro2circular.org
Project Duration	October 2021 – September 2024 (36 months)

Deliverable No.	D1.7
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 1 – A2C Specifications, Residues Management and Data Integration System
Task	T1.3 – A2C water and energy efficiency assurance
Lead beneficiary	11 (REG)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	10 (WETS), 12 (CEW)
Due date of deliverable	31 th December 2021
Actual submission date	31 th December 2021

* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

Document history

V	Date	Comments
v0.1	21/12/2021	First draft of document
v0.2	22/12/2021	Revised version based on the comments CETEC
v1.0	28/12/2021	First final version, approved by the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.
v1.1	23/11/2023	Revised version based on the REPA1 comments from the Project Officer
v2.0	24/11/2023	Reviewed final version, approved by the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.

Document Distribution Log

Version	Date	Distributed to
v0.1	21/12/2021	CETEC and CTNC for peer review
V1.1	23/11/2023	Coordinator

Verification and approval

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	Jaime Ortíz (CETEC)	24/11/23
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó (CETEC)	24/11/23

Disclaimer and acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement. No 101036838

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the views of the author(s) the European Research Executive Agency (REA) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. Whilst efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and completeness of this document, the A2C consortium shall not be liable for any errors or omissions, however caused.

Table of contents

Technical references	2
Table of contents	5
List of Tables	6
List of Figures	6
List of abbreviations	8
Glossary	9
Executive summary	12
1 Introduction	14
1.1 Objectives and scope of the deliverable	16
1.2 Link with other activities	16
1.3 Methodology	19
2 Energy recommendations	21
2.1 Energy optimisation	22
2.2 Energy Efficiency (EE)	23
2.2.1 Introduction to Energy Efficiency	23
2.2.2 Energy efficiency in the agricultural sector	28
2.2.3 Processes involved in the A2C project	31
2.2.4 General recommendations	33
2.3 Renewable energies	48
2.3.1 Energy generation from renewable sources	48
2.3.2 Renewable energies in the agricultural sector	55
2.3.3 A2C processes implementation	57
3 Water recommendations	65

3.1	Water issues related to agriculture	65
3.2	Water in the circular economy	66
3.3	Description of Agro2Circular processes	68
3.3.1	Process descriptions: Agrifood wastes treatment.....	69
3.3.2	Process descriptions: Multilayer plastic waste treatment	69
3.4	Recommendations	70
3.4.1	Methodology.....	70
3.4.2	Available treatment technologies.....	72
3.4.3	Preliminary recommendations	81
4	Conclusions	83
5	References	85

List of Tables

Table 1.	Typical excess air to achieve the highest efficiency. Source: [28].....	37
Table 2.	Renewable Energy Indicators 2020. Source: [15].....	50
Table 3.	Pros and cons of renewable sources.	64

List of Figures

Figure 1.	Deliverable’s structure	14
Figure 2.	Average annual precipitations in Spanish provinces’ capitals. Source: [13]	15
Figure 3.	Use of EE recommendations in A2C project.....	18
Figure 4.	Use of water recommendations in A2C project.....	19
Figure 5.	Global GHG emissions by sector. Source: [16].....	21
Figure 6.	Guide for optimization of energy consumption.....	23
Figure 7.	Transformation of energy to its final use.	25
Figure 8.	Transformation and use of energy in an industrial plant.	27

Figure 9. Final energy consumption by sector in the European Union. Data of 2019. Source: [19].....	28
Figure 10. Energy consumption in agri-food systems, by region, 2000-2018. Source: [20]	29
Figure 11. Agriculture development. Source: [23].....	30
Figure 12. Relationship between excess air and increased efficiency. Source: [28].....	36
Figure 13. IE classification by the IEC 60034-30-1, 2014.	46
Figure 14. Photovoltaic installation costs as a function of time. Source: [52].....	58
Figure 15. Wind onshore installation costs as a function of time. Source: [52]	59
Figure 16. Wind offshore installation costs as a function of time. Source: [52]	59
Figure 17. Biomass installation costs as a function of time. Source: [52]	60
Figure 18. Solar thermal installation costs as a function of time. Source: [52].....	61
Figure 19. A schematic representation of flocculation and sedimentation. Source: [65]....	73
Figure 20. A schematic representation of the process of coagulation. Source: [66]	74
Figure 21. A schematic representation of the flows in a hydrocyclone. Source: [72]	75
Figure 22. An overview of particles rejected by different classes of membranes. Source: [67]	76
Figure 23. An overview of rejected substances by different membrane classes. Source: [68]	77
Figure 24. A schematic overview of an electrodialysis stack, showing the movement of ions over the membranes and the half-reactions at the electrodes. Source: [69].....	78
Figure 25. Schematic representation of membrane distillation. Source: [70].....	79

List of abbreviations

A2C: Agro2Circular

CM: Condition Monitoring

CTNC: Centro Tecnológico Nacional de la Conserva

EAE: Enzymatic hydrolysis Assisted Extraction

EC: European Commission

EE: Energy Efficiency

GHG: Greenhouse Gas

LCA: Life Cycle Assessment

MAE: Microwaves Assisted Extraction

PV: Photovoltaic

PVS: Photovoltaic System

RES: Renewable Energy Systems

TRL: Technology Readiness Level

WWTP: Wastewater Treatment Plants

Glossary

Even though some of the terms included in this glossary can be general and considered of common knowledge by technicians or experts in the energy field, they may be unknown or vague to the general public. As this is a public deliverable, it is considered that offering a set of terms that help understand the information explained throughout the deliverable can be of general interest.

Energy

Energy means all forms of energy products, combustible fuels, heat, renewable energy, electricity, or any other form of energy [1].

Work

Defined as the change in the state of motion of a body due to the action of a force. In the case of mechanical work, it corresponds to the action of a force that generates a change in position, the work being the resultant of the product of the force and the distance travelled [2].

Power

It corresponds to the flow of energy per unit of time, the amount of work that can be done per unit of time. It can also be understood as a rate of consumption, release or generation of energy [2].

Energy Efficiency

Energy Efficiency means using less energy to perform the same task through behaviour change or energy-saving technologies. Many benefits are associated with energy efficiency, including a reduction in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, reduced demand for imported energy, and lower energy costs [3]. Energy efficiency is measured as the amount of energy output for a given energy input and listed as a percentage between 0% and 100%, for example the amount of mechanical energy that an electric motor produces for a given input of electrical energy [4].

Water Efficiency

Water Efficiency means using less water to perform the same task through behaviour change or water-saving or reuse technologies. Many benefits are associated with water efficiency, including a reduction in energy use associated with treating and moving water and the associated GHG emissions, reduced demand for treated water, and lower water costs [3].

Renewable Energy

Renewable Energy relates to energy generation from non-fossil fuel-based, natural sources that are constantly replenished, such as solar, wind, wave, tidal, geothermal, and biomass [3].

Primary energy

Primary energy means energy from renewable and non-renewable sources which has not undergone any conversion or transformation process [5].

Photovoltaic technology

Photovoltaic technology is based on the photovoltaic (PV) effect, in which a potential difference (voltage) appears between two layers of a semiconductor slice in which the conductivities are opposite, or between a semiconductor and a metal, under the effect of a light stream [6]. PV panels are the main technology developed using this effect.

Wind energy

Wind energy is that energy generated by using the kinetic energy of the wind to move a turbine, thus transforming kinetic energy into mechanical energy first and then electricity. A minimum wind speed is required for turbines to start working, and for safety reasons, they stop when this speed is too high.

Biomass

Biomass is renewable organic matter that comes from plants and animals [7]. Some authors define it as organic matter that can be converted into energy [8]. This definition includes

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

food crops, crop residues, wood waste, algae, and other products such as food waste or municipal solid waste.

Hydraulic energy

Hydraulic energy is the energy that can be obtained from water's movement. It is generally obtained when there is a course of water at a higher altitude than another [9]. A turbine is placed at the lowest course so that its rotor turns when water falls.

Solar thermal energy

Solar thermal energy produces energy using solar radiation. However, unlike photovoltaic energy, the produced energy is thermal instead of electrical. Collectors used in these systems can be classified as low-, medium- or high-temperature collectors, with different uses for the heat in each case [10].

Biogas

Biogas is a mixture of methane, carbon dioxide and small quantities of other gases produced by anaerobic digestion of organic matter in an oxygen-free environment. Its precise composition depends on the type of feedstock and the production pathway. When biogas' quality is improved from a 50-75% of methane content to a 94-99,9%, it is considered biomethane [11].

Hydrogen

Hydrogen is the simplest atom of the universe, and also the most abundant element in the universe as the sun and other stars are formed of hydrogen and helium. It is also present in many organic molecules forming bonds with other elements. However, it is not usual to find hydrogen molecules in the environment [12]. Hydrogen can be produced using water and electricity and then transformed again in these, which makes a good energy storage solution out of it.

Executive summary

Deliverable D1.7 establishes a set of recommendations on energy efficiency (use of renewable energy technologies and energy key parameters optimisation) and sustainable water & wastewater management (preliminary water demand, water quality criteria and wastewater characteristics) for the A2C processes and technologies.

The objective of the deliverable is to ensure that these transformations become sustainable processes with the lowest environmental impact. To this end, it is essential that all processes reuse as much water as possible, use as low energy as possible and the energy they use comes from renewable sources.

These processes are still at a medium Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and are therefore not implemented on a large scale. Because of this, the A2C processes are still in the design phase, so it is the right time to consider all the measures that can be taken to optimise them and make them as energy efficient as possible, which will also have an impact on improving their economic viability.

With regard to energy efficiency, a series of generic recommendations are described throughout the deliverable, focusing on the reduction of process demand, the need for maintenance and controls once the processes are implemented on a larger scale, the incorporation of the most efficient equipment and the importance of energy monitoring. Due to the fact that the specific equipment involved in each process are not yet available, generic recommendations have been made for heating, cooling and compressed air equipment, as well as electric motors. Later, once the necessary information has been obtained, specific measures related to energy efficiency will be suggested for each process. The renewable energies described are solar, wind, biomass, biogas, hydroelectric, solar thermal, combination of several and hydrogen, although it is considered that for the processes of the A2C project the most suitable renewable energy sources are solar, wind, biomass, biogas and hydrogen.

Regarding water management and efficiency, both the water and the resources that could be recovered from the water have to be considered. A methodology is discussed to come

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

to a set of recommendations for the various processes that are part of the A2C project. A list of the processes involved is included, and suggestions are made of possible water treatment technologies that could be used to make water suitable for reuse. The technologies discussed are flotation/sedimentation, coagulation and flocculation, hydrocyclones, filtration and membranes, electro dialysis, membrane distillation, mechanical vapor recompression and adsorption. A general set of recommendations is given at this moment. In the future, both the list of possible technologies and the recommendations can be expanded and fine-tuned.

The deliverable D1.7 is a public and open deliverable. An identification of the situation of A2C processes in terms of energy efficiency and water management is proposed for future implementation.

1 Introduction

The present report is a public deliverable (*Deliverable D1.7 – Energy and Water Recommendations*) of the Agro2Circular (A2C) H2020 funded European project which corresponds to task 3 (*T1.3 - A2C water and energy efficiency assurance*) of work package 1 (*WP1 - A2C Specifications, Residues Management and Data Integration System*).

This deliverable addresses, from an environmental point of view, the collateral issues of the introduction of new industrial processes due to the increase of energy and water consumption, even though those processes are devised to improve the environment through the revaluation of residues.

The following structure will be followed in the deliverable to address this issue:

Figure 1. Deliverable's structure

Throughout this deliverable, special focus will be put on water and energy efficiency. This project's demonstrators are located in Murcia, in south-eastern Spain. Weather in this region

is especially dry, with very little rain registered throughout the year. This can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Average annual precipitations in Spanish provinces' capitals. Source: [13]

As a result, water is a scarce resource that requires special attention when used in industry, taking water efficiency measures to reduce consumption as much as possible. On the other hand, the Region of Murcia finds the Mediterranean Sea at its south border, something this region has used to obtain the water it lacks by developing water desalinations plants. These plants, despite being useful, require an important amount of energy to work (around 3 kWh/m³ of water [14]) and thus energy efficiency measures must be taken to reduce energy consumption as much as possible. The use of renewable energy sources is key too when ecology is considered, reducing the impact on the environment of these activities. Precisely, due to the lack of rain in Murcia, it is a very suitable location for renewable energies such as photovoltaic installations. This situation could be similar in other European locations, be it due to the lack of water, be it due to the requirement of reducing impact on the environment or due to the reduction of energy resources such as natural gas as a consequence of current wars.

1.1 Objectives and scope of the deliverable

The A2C project aims to upgrade the value chain in the agriculture sector by revaluing plastic and organic wastes such as plastic barriers, multilayer food packaging and organic residues (fruits and vegetables as grapes, citrus, broccoli, etc.). Although this revaluation process will allow the circularity in the agriculture sector reducing the waste generated with the positive impact on the environment, some energy and water consuming equipment have to be used with their corresponding carbon and water footprint.

In order to mitigate this issue, T1.3 aims to assess the energy and water consumption of the new processes in order to identify and select the best practices and technologies that will allow the best energy and water efficiency performance.

A description of the best energy practices and technologies on the agricultural sector is not the goal of this deliverable, but rather the application of these on the processes proposed during A2C project, aiming to reduce the impact of this sector on the environment. However, a superficial approach on these matters applied to the agricultural sector will be offered.

Therefore, the purpose of this deliverable is the realisation of a set of recommendations to be used by A2C partners. These recommendations will focus on energy efficiency (use of renewable energy technologies and energy key parameters optimization) and sustainable water & wastewater management (preliminary water demand, water quality criteria and wastewater characteristics) for the A2C processes and technologies to ensure that these transformations become sustainable processes with the lowest environmental impact. To this end, it is essential that all processes reuse as much water as possible, use as low energy as possible and that the energy they use comes from renewable sources.

1.2 Link with other activities

WP1 aims to achieve the definition of the specifications and strategies for the preparation of the new products and recycled materials of A2C project, as well as the definition of the residues management and Data Integration System. The specific objectives of WP1 are (i) to define the specifications of the new products along the value chain, (ii) to establish

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

strategies for compliance assessment with standards and prepare the recycled materials food contact approval, (iii) to define recommendations on water and energy for the new technologies and processes, (iv) to perform a management plan for the different residues, (v) to characterise the residues, and (vi) to develop the A2C Data Integration System-DIS.

The present deliverable is clearly aligned with objective (iii), being the first report to set up the concept of efficiency in energy and water management in the form of recommendations. The outputs of Deliverable 1.7 will be the starting point for the implementation of water and energy efficient management in the A2C project:

In energy efficiency:

Deliverable 1.7 will be one of the inputs for deliverable 1.8 (D1.8. – Energy Management Plan (Draft), M12) and deliverable 1.9 (D1.9 – Energy Management Plan (Final), M24) also corresponding to task 3 of WP1. The scope of both deliverables is the analysis of the energy requirements of the A2C technologies and processes including time of use, life cycle and load, aiming to optimise the key parameters to reach the maximum energy savings. Moreover, the combined outputs of D1.7, D1.8 and D1.9, will serve as the basis for the energy performance in A2C demonstrators which will be carried out in Task 6.2 (T6.2 – A2C demonstrators, WP6 – Demonstration of the A2C technological solution) by means of studying energy consumption analysis, electrical parameters, loads and renewable energies integration in order to recommend the most efficient industrial solutions, which will be reported in deliverable 6.3. (D6.3 – A2C Demonstrators of the technologies and prototypes of the valorised products at relevant scale and industrial relevant environment to demonstrate A2C solution at TRL6-7, including energy performance (M33)).

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

Figure 3. Use of EE recommendations in A2C project.

In sustainable water & wastewater management:

Regarding the water management recommendations, deliverable 1.7 will be an input for WP3, WP5 and WP6. In task 3.1 (Plastic waste pretreatments and preliminary decontamination), the information and data collected in this deliverable will be used to design a water treatment system. In tasks 3.3 (Physical recycling of complex multilayers containing aluminium), 3.4 (Enzymatic recycling of multilayer structures based on PE/PET) and 3.5 (Mechanical recycling of simple multilayer structures and products from physical recycling) the water management recommendations can be included in designing and upscaling the processes on a pilot scale. In task 5.1 (Upcycling of products (TPA, EG, alkanes) obtained from the enzymatic degradation), the recommendations will be used as a basis for the recovery of water and salt from the production of PHBV and carotenoids. The information from deliverable 1.7, through the results acquired from WP3 and WP5, will be integrated in the A2C demonstrators' site of WP6.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

Figure 4. Use of water recommendations in A2C project.

1.3 Methodology

The methodology of the deliverable includes the following main activities:

- A description of renewable energy sources and energy efficiency strategies that can be applied in agriculture to reduce the activity's impact on the environment.
- Identification of the characteristics of A2C processes and technologies within the scope of water and energy.
- A comprehensive literature review of generic energy efficiency strategies at industrial level, taking into account the specific A2C processes and technologies.
- The identification and description of the most suitable renewable energy sources to promote the energy efficiency of the A2C project processes and technologies.
- Description of promising water treatment technologies, focused on delivering clean water and recovering resources

Deliverable D1.7 has been developed at the beginning of the A2C project with the purpose of being used as a research document for the energy and water efficiency works that will be

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

done during the project. The tasks and deliverables that will be fed with the information of D1.7 have been indicated in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that collection of some energy and water consumption data from the demonstrators, which will complement this deliverable, will be done in common with *Task 7.3 Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring*, which will be documented in *D7.6 Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring (Draft)* and *D7.7 Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring*, as T1.3 and T7.3 have some inputs in common. Thus, the works for T1.3 and T7.3 need to be aligned.

2.1 Energy optimisation

Achieving optimal energy efficiency in a process is a multifaceted endeavour that involves strategic considerations at various stages. The process begins with meticulous design optimization aimed at eliminating superfluous steps and ensuring a streamlined workflow. By scrutinizing the entire process, process designers can identify and eliminate unnecessary stages, thereby reducing energy consumption from the outset.

A significant aspect of energy optimization lies in reducing overall energy demand. This can be accomplished through the enhancement of energy efficiency in the equipment employed throughout the process. Upgrading technologies, fine-tuning operational parameters, and adopting state-of-the-art, energy-efficient machinery contribute to a substantial reduction in energy requirements. This not only results in cost savings but also aligns with sustainability goals by lessening the overall environmental impact.

Another integral strategy involves the reutilization of energy. Rather than considering energy losses as inevitable, forward-thinking designs harness these losses to power other stages or processes within the system. This approach, known as energy reuse or cogeneration, maximizes the utility of energy within the processes. By capturing and repurposing energy that would otherwise be wasted, this method significantly improves overall efficiency and resource utilization.

Furthermore, once completed all of the previous strategies, the incorporation of renewable energies, such as solar, wind, or hydropower, helps with the reduction of reliance on fossil fuels and also mitigates the environmental impacts of the processes.

The following schema summarizes the steps to be follow to optimize the energy consumption of processes:

Figure 6. Guide for optimization of energy consumption.

2.2 Energy Efficiency (EE)

2.2.1 Introduction to Energy Efficiency

The integration of thermodynamic principles, sustainability considerations and a deep understanding of energy concepts is essential when designing new processes. A commitment to energy efficiency not only aligns with environmental responsibility but also ensures economic viability and social well-being. As we chart the course for future innovations, a holistic and principled approach will be the catalyst for sustainable progress.

2.2.1.1 Energy principles

In the realm of engineering and process design, adherence to the laws of thermodynamics is the cornerstone of achieving optimal efficiency and performance. These fundamental principles govern energy transfer and conversion, providing invaluable insights into the behaviour of systems. By understanding and applying the laws of thermodynamics, engineers can navigate the complexities of energy transformation, ensuring that processes are not only effective but also sustainable.

Energy is defined as the capacity to execute external actions, to generate changes or to initiate a movement. In physics it is the ability to do "work". The concept of energy is closely linked to the concept of motion (or change). Energy can manifest itself in different forms and do different kinds of work. Among other distinctions we have: chemical energy, thermal energy, mechanical energy, internal energy, electromagnetic energy, electrical energy and nuclear energy [2].

Energy must obey the two laws of thermodynamics:

- The first law of thermodynamics

Energy cannot be created or destroyed (which is called the conservation of energy); however, it can be transformed from one type into another. In fact, every useful process transforms energy from one form to another. There are many different forms or types of energy.

- The second law of thermodynamics

The Second Law of Thermodynamics sets out the specific idea that heat cannot be converted entirely to mechanical energy, as previously mentioned [17].

2.2.1.2 Social, economic and environmental sustainability

The importance of social, economic, and environmental sustainability cannot be overstated in today's interconnected world. As we strive for progress, it is imperative to consider the broader impact of our actions. Adhering to sustainability principles ensures that advancements do not come at the expense of social well-being, economic stability, or environmental health. It is a holistic approach that recognises the interdependence of these factors, acknowledging that true progress must be inclusive and enduring.

Energy, as a resource, must contribute to the three pillars of sustainability:

- Social sustainability: Energy provides social wellbeing because it offers us services of great value: comfort, mobility, etc. For this reason, access to energy must be guaranteed for the entire population in conditions of quality, safety and competitiveness.
- Economic sustainability: Energy is present in all economic activity, is a determining factor in business competitiveness and must in itself generate economic activity (companies in the energy sector).
- Environmental sustainability: Energy generation and consumption processes must be environmentally friendly in order to ensure its conservation [18].

2.2.1.3 Primary energy vs. Final energy

When designing a new process, a clear grasp of concepts such as primary and final energy is paramount. Primary energy represents the raw, unconverted forms of energy, while final energy is the refined and usable output. Efficient processes minimise the gap between primary and final energy, maximising the utility of resources. This not only optimises energy usage but also contributes to economic efficiency by reducing waste.

Furthermore, understanding thermal energy and specific consumption is crucial for designing processes that harness energy effectively. Thermal energy, a key player in many industrial processes, requires meticulous management to prevent losses and inefficiencies. Specific consumption metrics provide a quantitative measure of efficiency, allowing engineers to fine-tune processes for optimal performance.

Energy comes in different forms and can be transformed into different types of energy for better use.

- Primary energies: chemical energy (coal, oil, natural gas), nuclear energy (uranium), solar energy (solar thermal, photovoltaic, wind) and gravitational energy (hydro, tidal).
- Final energies (energy vectors): electrical energy, gasoline, diesel, propane, natural gas.

Figure 7. Transformation of energy to its final use.

In each transformation process, part of the energy that is consumed is lost/transformed into other non-desired types of energy. The transport of energy involves losses: heat, pressure loss, electrical resistance, friction, etc.

2.2.1.4 Deep in the concept of energy efficiency

Energy efficiency, which is often roughly defined by the simple ratio energy efficiency useful output of a process divided by the energy input to a process:

$$\text{energy efficiency} = \frac{\text{useful output of a process}}{\text{energy input to a process}}$$

does not represent the unique quantitative definition of energy efficiency. Therefore, in order to determine the energy efficiency of any processes, it is necessary to adopt one or more definitions. Two energy efficiency indicators are usually used:

- Thermal efficiency: which is a thermodynamic indicator that shows how much a process deviates from a theoretical optimum.
- Specific energy consumption: which is a physical-thermodynamic indicator that represents the energy used per unit of product.

For steady-state processes, thermal efficiency is the ratio of energy output to energy input:

$$\eta = \frac{E_{out}}{E_{in}}$$

where the energy output E_{out} is the useful effect and the energy input E_{in} is the necessary expense. Thermal efficiency expresses the amount of energy input converted into useful energy by the process. The difference between input and output corresponds to the total losses of the system. Therefore, the useful effect, E_{out} , can also be interpreted as the theoretical energy requirement, i.e., without losses. For the same process, specific energy consumption is the ratio of energy input to the output measured in physical units:

$$q = \frac{E_{in}}{V}$$

In general, the energy system of a process plant comprises the generation system of energy carriers from the imported energies, and the utilisation system of these generated energy carriers in relation to the variables which affect their consumptions (energy drivers). [7]

Figure 8. Transformation and use of energy in an industrial plant.

As energy is degraded and losses can be found in any real process in which energy is involved and in any transformation that it suffers, adopting energy efficiency actions is a must. Energy efficiency refers to the use of less energy to perform the same task or produce the same result. It is a key element to reduce any organisation or activity's impact on the environment, because:

- While energy efficiency decreases the amount of energy required in the process, non-renewable energy consumed is reduced.
- As the total amount of energy required in the process is reduced, efforts to substitute non-renewable energy sources by renewable ones are lowered.

The approach to achieve energy efficiency depends significantly on the process that is under study. Some processes such as those in oil & gas industries may require high temperatures, making thermal isolation a key action to implement. In those processes in which engines or pumps have a significant weight over total energy consumption it is important to size them properly, to use low-consumption devices or to include variable-frequency drives.

Energy efficiency actions applied to the agricultural sector and the A2C processes will be discussed in the following points.

2.2.2 Energy efficiency in the agricultural sector

As it was shown in Figure 5, agriculture and related activities account for nearly 18.4% of global GHG emissions, while consuming around 2.9% of the total final energy consumed in the European Union, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Final energy consumption by sector in the European Union. Data of 2019. Source: [19]

When speaking of the whole agrifood sector, it reaches 30% of the total energy demand globally. It must be noted that, even though energy consumption in this sector has been stable in most of the world for the last 15 years, a consistent increase has been experienced in Asia, and is likely to take place at some moment in Africa as developing countries increase their population and production.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

Figure 10. Energy consumption in agri-food systems, by region, 2000-2018. Source: [20]

Agricultural energy demand can be divided into direct and indirect energy needs [21]. Direct energy needs include those required for land preparation, cultivation, irrigation, harvesting, post-harvest processing, food production, storage and transport, whereas indirect energy needs are those in the form of sequestered energy in fertilisers, herbicides, pesticides and other products required by the crops.

Through the A2C project, some activities are proposed to reduce the impact of industrial residues on the environment. More specifically, in this deliverable, actions and recommendations to mitigate the energy and water impact of these activities are offered. However, further reductions could be achieved by taking actions related to direct and indirect energy requirements. Under this paradigm, energy efficiency can be key to improve sustainability in the agricultural sector.

Agriculture is an activity that in some cases is carried out by people who do not have technology as present as those working in industries. It is usual that agricultural exploitations have out-of-date equipment with little automatization and none monitorization of variables. As a result, there are a set of low cost or even free opportunities for energy saving that can be generally applied to agriculture [22]:

- Switching off all energy consuming equipment that is not in use.
- Performing the appropriate maintenance of the existing machinery.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

- Implementing predictive and preventive maintenance instead of only corrective maintenance.
- Using control systems by monitoring variables such as humidity or temperature.
- Replacing conventional lamps for LED lights.
- Install occupancy sensors.
- Replacing out-of-date and high-consuming equipment for more modern machines with better performance.
- When using pumping systems, implementing variable-frequency drives if needed to adapt the device's performance to the real requirements.
- If possible, using gravity-fed water systems instead of pumped systems.

The adoption of automatization solutions leads to Agriculture 3.0, improving productivity and reducing resources consumption. Agriculture 4.0 includes internet of things solutions and artificial intelligence, allowing a remote control or even independent crops to some extent. Agriculture 5.0 adopts new energy sources and even combines energy production and agricultural activities in the same land. By following this evolution, a more sustainable agriculture can be achieved.

Figure 11. Agriculture development. Source: [23]

2.2.3 Processes involved in the A2C project

The A2C project develops processes with electrical and thermal demand. Most of the needs are related to:

- Mechanical movements for transporting of materials in conveyor belts, grilling, pumping of fluids, centrifugation, etc.
- Increase of temperature for water evaporation or for increasing the reaction speed.

The energy efficiency recommendations address the following processes, which are classified according to their purpose:

i) Extraction and purification of bioactive substances from Fruit and Vegetables (F&V) wastes by a hybrid strategy of green solvents and sustainable advanced extraction technologies.

- Innovative extraction and purification strategies for bioactive substances from the F&V wastes:
 - Extractions routes: Green solvents + ultrasounds assisted extraction and green solvents + enzymatic hydrolysis + MW assisted extraction.
 - Purification technologies: Membrane filtration and membrane filtration + adsorption.

ii) Production of a range of new formulations using the bioactive substances extracted from wastes for their application in cosmetic, nutraceuticals and food.

- Design a specific strategy in each case to achieve high stability of the extracts for further industrialisation.
- The extracted highly stable bioactive compounds will be validated in a real environment by end users preparing formulations to demonstrate our solution in an operational environment.

iii) Recycling of the multilayer plastics coming from agriculture and post-industrial packaging.

- Optical sorting of the multilayers by a synergistic combination of technologies.
- Physical separation of the Aluminium from the multilayers based on SAPE patented delamination technology.
- Enzymatic depolymerisation of the PE/PET multilayers by a synergic strategy of customisation of enzymes and plastic wastes pre-treatments.
- Plastics decontamination for the reintroduction of the recycled plastics into the agrifood value chain (packaging and agricultural films) by 3 step process of washing, micro/nanoplastics separation and vacuum extrusion.
- Aluminium purification and treatment for reuse. Aluminium from the physical separation will be chemically modified.
- The simple multilayers and the plastic mono-materials obtained from the physical recycling will be formulated for their application in food packaging and agricultural films.

iv) Upcycling of the recycled plastics coming from agriculture and post-industrial packaging to obtain high added value materials.

- Upcycling of enzymatic degradation products (alkanes, TPA, EG) by biotransformation to obtain high added value building blocks for cosmetics.
- PHBV bioplastics and carotenoids production by cell factory: The by-products of the previous cell factories in combination with organic waste from the agrifood industry will be used as nutrients.
- Development of plastic compounds for food packaging and agriculture:
 - Development of recyclable high barrier PE plastic compounds as an alternative to current non-recyclable multilayers.
 - Development of PHBV bioplastics compounds. The neat PHBV range obtained will be formulated and compounded for their application in flexible food packaging and agricultural films development.

2.2.4 General recommendations

As mentioned before, the objective of the energy efficiency is about minimising energy consumption achieving the same desired aim. The actions that contribute to highly energy-efficient processes are detailed below:

2.2.4.1 Energy demand reduction

These actions are focused on the design or redesign of systems and processes, both physical and operational. The aim of this section is to put on record the importance of decisions in planning and operating production systems in energy efficiency.

Planning a production system starts with the definition of production processes and the selection of available technologies. Defining each process step imposes technological limitations on succeeding steps. In order to design energy efficient systems, besides each single process step, the consumption of the whole process chain has to be taken into account. In addition, exploiting energy regeneration and recovery cycles requires a detailed understanding of the consumption behaviour of the involved processes.

After selecting processes and technologies, appropriate equipment and the layout of the planned system are determined in an iterative process of defining, evaluating and selecting alternative designs. Here, energy efficiency objectives such as minimising total consumption or energy recovery have to be integrated into the evaluation and decision processes.

Scheduling assigns products and processes to available production equipment and influences the energy consumption behaviour of the whole system. By integrating energy efficiency criteria into scheduling, a reduction of energy costs is to be expected. Such criteria and metrics are for instance peak demand shifting, adapting the production programme to external conditions such as energy prices or renewable energy availability and automatically turning equipment off when stand-by time thresholds are reached and scheduling constraints are fulfilled. A prerequisite for the integration of energy efficiency criteria in planning activities is a detailed prediction of the energy consumption. This prediction has to be carried out on a machine level, i.e., the energy consumption of each machine and product

has to be calculated. Moreover, approaches such as load levelling and peak shaving require high time domain resolution of energy consumption; the different operating states of the machines have to be taken into account.

In such ways, system-wide consumption and cost estimations as well as comparison of alternative equipment during system design, can be based on analytical models. Aggregating the predicted consumptions for different levels of a factory's organisational structure allows for a centralised energy management [24].

2.2.4.2 Maintenance and control

A maintenance plan, apart from benefiting operational continuity, service standards and productivity, has a decisive impact on the energy consumption. Controlling the energy consumption of different equipment and systems should also be part of routine maintenance tasks.

As irrespective of the area of business and supplied product, each process has technical resources (machines, equipment) that require maintenance in operation. By maintaining we wish them to perform the tasks ordered by the user efficiently, i.e. with the optimum use of resources (materials, energy, etc.) [25].

Many basic tasks of minor complexity and low implementation cost can have a great impact on energy efficiency, generating large reductions in energy consumption, such as:

- Cleaning routines: evaporative condensers, filters of thermal conditioning systems, steam generators, exchangers, etc.
- Inspection and repair routines for fluid leaks: compressed air, water, compressed gases, steam, etc.
- Routines for inspection and repair of insulation.
- Inspection and repair routines for steam traps.
- Water treatment for steam generators, evaporative condensers and cooling towers.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

Within a maintenance plan, monitoring tasks of different conditions and/or operating parameters of the machines and installations must be foreseen in order to be able to detect when there is a deviation.

In these terms, the concept of Condition Monitoring (CM) arises to facilitate predictive maintenance works. CM is a process consisting of monitoring parameters of condition in machinery (vibration, temperature etc.), in order to identify a significant change which is indicative of the initial stage of a failure. In this sense, CM can be used to monitor the performance of equipment by measuring and tracking certain physical parameters in order to anticipate failure:

- Monitoring the dynamic conditions of the machinery: vibrations.
- Temperature Monitoring.
- Infrared Thermography Inspection.
- Measurement of equipment performance:
 - Pressure
 - Flow rate
 - Power output
 - Power consumption
 - Fuel consumption

The major benefit is to achieve an early warning in order to schedule a corrective intervention in order to minimise the consequences, i.e., overconsumption of energy.

Many failures with wear related failure modes will also cause an increase in energy consumption during the initial stages. By implementing condition monitoring techniques to detect failures in their early stage, you will also contribute to the care of energy efficiency.

The effectiveness and quality of the corrective action is essential to avoid including elements that cause additional failures after the repair, thus further decreasing reliability and energy efficiency [26].

2.2.4.3 Incorporation of efficient technologies

One of the basic measures that achieves significant energy savings in any process is, in one hand, the incorporation of efficient technologies that meet production needs while reducing energy consumption and make it possible to take advantage of existing and free energy resources and/or wasted energy resources and, in the other hand, the automation of the systems to modulate capacity and minimise uptime.

2.2.4.3.1 Thermal installations: boilers, ovens, dryers, etc.

2.2.4.3.1.1 Control of combustion

The control of combustion is a basic measure in any heat generator using fossil fuel. The control of the combustion that is produced inside the burners aims to release as much energy as possible from the fuel, causing complete combustion with adequate excess air, and therefore minimising the amount of energy lost in the combustion fumes.

One of the most decisive factors for good combustion is the excess air. It is calculated theoretically and then increased by a factor that marks the good practice of this equipment and depends on the type of fuel. This excess must be controlled, because as it increases, and once complete combustion has been achieved, its increase will only lead to increasing energy losses through the gases expelled [27].

Figure 12. Relationship between excess air and increased efficiency. Source: [28]

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

To implement this measure, the burner and the primary and secondary air fans must be adjusted in order to obtain the lowest possible loss of unburned fuel. Once these parameters have been calculated, combustion control must be carried out by analysing the combustion gases at certain intervals in order to achieve the desired gas concentration.

To carry out the analysis of this combustion, fixed or mobile gas analysers are installed, depending on whether it is measured continuously or with a certain frequency (which will depend on the power of the equipment), at the combustion fume outlet. Once the percentage of oxygen content in the fumes has been obtained, the amount of air and fuel entering the combustion is regulated. In addition, a carbon monoxide (CO) analyser can also be installed, as the presence of CO is an indication of incomplete combustion

The implementation of a controller is usually the most optimal solution to continuously regulate and control the fuel and air input to the combustion. This equipment receives the signal from the analyser and, depending on the difference between this signal and the reference signal calculated based on the boiler load, acts on the air regulation. The excess air to achieve the highest energy efficiency in typical fuels are [27]:

FUEL	MINIMUM %	MAXIMUM %
Natural gas	5	10
Fuel oil	5	20
Coal	15	60

Table 1. Typical excess air to achieve the highest efficiency. Source: [28]

2.2.4.3.1.2 Steam boiler blowdown minimisation

Steam generation boiler blowdowns are carried out with the aim of eliminating the solids or salts that are generated when the water evaporates, which were previously dissolved in it. These solids accumulate and make it necessary to use more energy to heat the water, as they are deposited on the walls, which reduces the contact between the surfaces and therefore the heat transfer. In addition to the higher energy consumption, if the solids are not purged, they will end up encrusted on the surfaces and corrode the equipment.

By blowdown, the water contained in the boiler is discharged and replaced with feed water so the blowdown should be kept to the minimum necessary, as any excess, in addition to increasing water consumption, represents an energy and economic loss as the feed water must be heated, treated and pumped. Excess boiler blowdown, in addition to increasing energy consumption, can lead to drainage.

The optimum amount of blowdown is determined by several factors such as boiler type, operating pressure, water treatment and feed water quality. To achieve the lowest losses due to blowdown, the blowdown flow rate should be reduced to the optimum amount.

2.2.4.3.1.3 Waste heat recovery from flue gas

Boiler economiser: Feedwater preheating

An economiser is a finned tube heat exchanger, which recovers part of the sensible heat from the combustion products emitted by a boiler and transfers it to the feed water, thus increasing thermal efficiency [29].

Boiler heat recovery system: Preheating of combustion air. In this case, the combustion air is heated with the combustion gases before it enters the generation equipment, thus reducing fuel consumption. By means of the recuperator, the performance of the equipment will be significantly improved.

Most furnaces produce fumes at high temperatures (250 – 1.000 °C) and there is a great potential for energy recovery and reuse in the process, reducing fuel consumption for the same power to be transferred.

A boiler water economiser is more economical than an air preheater for small boilers, i.e., low pressure boilers and with a steam production of less than 20.000 kg/h. The air preheater will compete with the water economiser for larger capacity and output units [27].

2.2.4.3.1.4 Minimising wall losses

It is interesting to know that the boiler loses heat through radiation and convection, even when the burner is not in operation, simply because the boiler, valves and piping, house steam at every moment and therefore they transfer heat to their surroundings [30].

To minimise wall losses, the walls are covered with highly insulating materials such as mineral wool. In spite of this, due to the large temperature differences between the inside of the boiler and the outside environment, losses due to this problem can be as high as 3% in some cases.

In addition to including a good insulation, it is necessary to maintain it in good condition over the years, as a deteriorated or damp insulation does not function as an insulator, but quite the opposite.

2.2.4.3.2 Steam generation and transmission facilities

2.2.4.3.2.1 Condensate and steam lines insulation

As mentioned in the previous section, there is a large temperature difference between the steam generated and the outside ambient temperature, so there will be energy losses in the form of heat.

During the distribution of the steam from the boiler to the consumption and return points, there is a large surface area of pipes that are at different temperatures with respect to the ambient temperature, so that if they are not insulated, enormous heat losses will be generated, which will be manifested by the need for greater fuel expenditure for steam generation and heating of the return steam. In addition, condensate may be produced in the lines and not enough steam may reach the consumption points.

It is therefore desirable, and in some cases mandatory, to implement this insulation, including boiler surfaces, pipes, tanks and fittings. In this way, heat losses can be reduced by up to 90%.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

In order to calculate the insulation thickness of a surface, it must be taken into account that the greater the thickness, the lower the losses that may occur, so that the amount of condensate decreases, and that the greater the insulation, the higher the investment cost required. In addition, the temperature difference between the steam and the outside, the velocities of both currents, the material, thickness, diameter and length of the pipe, its location and the ambient conditions must be taken into account.

2.2.4.3.2.2 Leakage reduction

Reducing steam leakage is one of the biggest potential energy and cost savings in industrial plants.

Steam leaks are often caused by poor maintenance of seals, fittings and areas that wear out over the years. These leaks are usually located in pipe joints, valves and traps. Leaks due to pipe failures are easily detectable and should be eliminated quickly, especially due to the risk they pose to operators. On the other hand, trap malfunctions are difficult to detect, especially in closed condensing systems where the trap discharge point is not easily accessible.

The main causes of steam leakage at flanged and threaded pipe/valve connections are: (1) stress from expansion and contraction of pipes due to the heat of the steam, (2) threaded components that have loosened due to that stress, and (3) deterioration of gaskets [31].

A facility maintenance programme aimed at finding and repairing leaks is essential for efficient operation of steam systems.

The amount of leaking steam in both mains and traps must be estimated.

Checking the operation of traps can be done by [27]:

- Visual inspection.
- Sight glass inspection.
- Thermal analysis.
- Acoustic monitoring. Cold production systems

2.2.4.3.2.3 Reduction of condensation temperature

In refrigeration circuits, when the condensing temperature in the condensers is high, the compressor work must be equally high to reach the required refrigerant pressure. This relationship between compression and condensing equipment must be considered in the efficient operation of the refrigeration system.

Depending on the refrigerant used, the variation in condensing temperature will impact on the energy consumption of the compressor, so adjustments to the condensing unit, aimed at a reduction of its condensing temperature, will save electrical energy in the compressor units. The coefficient of performance improves with a lower condensing temperature.

The aim of this recommendation is to reduce the work of the compressor by reducing the condensing pressure at which the refrigeration cycle operates. This results in lower energy consumption of the compressor. Other benefits can also be obtained, such as lower discharge temperature and increased compressor life due to less extreme conditions.

There are several courses of action to reduce the condensing temperature:

- Change of condenser type: There are different types of condensers for the same purpose, each of which will give a different condensing temperature.
- Variable pressure control: Normally, fixed condensing pressure controls adjusted to the most unfavourable conditions of the year are used. The measure is to remove the fixed control and allow the condensation to fluctuate with the ambient conditions.
- Evaporative pre-cooling of the condenser cooling air: This reduces the inlet temperature of the refrigerant.

2.2.4.3.2.4 Evaporating temperature increase

The cooling capacity of a compressor, and therefore of a refrigeration circuit, basically depends on two temperatures: the evaporating temperature and the condensing temperature. When the condensing temperature drops, the cooling capacity increases. When the evaporating temperature rises, so does the cooling capacity [32].

Therefore, as the evaporating temperature increases, the work that the compressor must do to evacuate the heat in the condenser decreases and, therefore, its consumption decreases. The measure to be taken is to maintain a floating evaporating pressure at the load conditions. This is achieved by means of electronic controllers, which are offered by certain manufacturers.

2.2.4.3.2.5 Load regulation on motors

Due to the fact that in cooling installations the demand is not linear and depends a lot on outdoor conditions and indoor needs, the ideal situation is having equipment that meets the needs and does not require to continuously stop and start (which significantly reduces the useful life of the equipment), which means a very high energy cost. In addition, many installations are oversized as the real needs are much lower. In order to achieve the lowest energy consumption, it is essential that the equipment works at the right point, adapting to the demand. For this, it is necessary:

- To have equipment (compressors, fans and pumps) of different power so that they can adjust in the best way to the load.
- The installation of variable frequency drives in electric motors, as these devices adapt the operation of the equipment to the most efficient point.

A frequency inverter is by definition an industrial controller that is located between the power supply and the motor. Mains power passes through the drive and regulates the power before it reaches the motor and then adjusts the frequency and voltage according to the requirements of the process.

Inverters reduce the power output of an application, such as a pump or fan, by controlling the speed of the motor, ensuring that it does not run faster than necessary [31].

This ensures that the equipment operates at its peak performance, regardless of the load.

2.2.4.3.3 Compressed air systems

2.2.4.3.3.1 Leakage reduction in compressed air networks

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

It is important that in compressed air installations the equipment (compressors) that produce the air, its complementary elements (filters, dryers, traps, etc.) and the network of distribution pipes are cared for, maintained and that the air generated by the compressor is used to the maximum.

The use of compressed air can be very costly, as in most industries compressed air is wasted once it has been generated, due to an increase in pressure loss as a result of poor filter maintenance, water/condensate removal, unadvised purging or air leaks.

In order to study the possible critical points and improvements to be made in an industrial compressed air installation, whether existing or in the design phase, it is necessary to consider different aspects that will allow us to obtain an efficient installation and achieve considerable economic savings.

Over time, the pipes and connections of an industrial compressed air network deteriorate and generate leaks, and it is essential to find them and repair them. Compressed air leaks cause unnecessary energy consumption that can be avoided by implementing a system that detects and repairs them as soon as possible.

The most common places where industrial compressed air leaks occur are usually:

- Quick release couplings
- Pipe and hose seals
- Regulating filters and lubricators
- Valves
- Pneumatic hand tools
- Industrial pneumatic installations

To detect and eliminate industrial leaks there are some simple methods of detection such as:

- Listening for the sound of the leak. This will work for large leaks that generate a high level of noise and assuming there is no excessive ambient sound, but its detection reliability is not guaranteed.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

- Spraying soapy water on the duct joints where the leak is suspected. If such a leak exists, bubbles will be generated. Sweeping the compressed air distribution network in an installation is time-consuming.
- Ultrasonic compressed air leak detection is one of the most accurate forms of compressed air leak detection. Ultrasonic detectors have an acoustic sensor that registers noise fluctuations and identifies the location and intensity of the leak to determine the size of the leak. It is a simple and fast detection method.

Most industrial compressed air leaks are created in the connections or joints of the elements, either because they are not properly sealed, because of poor quality parts or because of degradation after many years. Repairing the leak is easy, simply replace the damaged part and install a suitable new one to prevent another compressed air leak in the future [33].

2.2.4.3.3.2 Reduction of air pressure to the minimum permissible

A good efficiency measure to save compressed air energy is to try to reduce the plant pressure so that the energy consumed by the system to compress the air is reduced.

In addition, pressure reduction generates a beneficial side effect in that, by sending less compressed air to unregulated uses and compressed air leakage, losses are reduced and thus the efficiency of the installation is increased.

To calculate the minimum supply pressure, it is first necessary to identify the accessories, tools and compressed air consumers, indicating their location in the plant and determining the conditions of their consumption, such as: air flow and supply or working pressure of the equipment, maximum level of humidity allowed in the air, particles and oil content. Then establish the percentage of operating time of each consumer and the number of consumers that can work simultaneously on each distribution line and on the main line. Then estimate the possible losses due to leakage, incorporating it in the calculation. And finally calculate the maximum pressure drop for each end point of consumption [34]. It can also be estimated more quickly by performing tests and measurements at the most unfavourable point of the network.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

To implement it, the compressor control range should be adjusted by lowering the setpoint pressures.

This measure can be easily applied to reciprocating and rotary screw compressors, and should only be considered when the difference between the compressor supply pressure and the working pressure of the equipment is greater than or equal to 0,7 bar. Exceptionally, it can be used in systems where the distribution network is very long or the pressure drops are very high.

Current control systems are capable of maintaining a low average pressure without exceeding the minimum pressure required for proper operation of all equipment.

Regardless of the quality of the control system, whether newly acquired or of a certain age, it is necessary to adjust the control range to the needs of the particular plant [27].

2.2.4.3.3.3 Air supply at the lowest possible temperature

This is a simple method of improving compressor performance. It consists of taking the intake air from outside the compressor room, taking it from a cool place as close as possible to the compressor.

The outside air is normally at a lower temperature than the air in the compressor room, as the latter receives the heat released by the compressor equipment. As the density of the outside air should be higher, this increases the mass flow rate delivered by the compressor and thus its efficiency.

It is important that the suction point is installed in a place where the air is as free as possible from particles, water or vapours from cooling towers, as both particles and water would cause condensate and wear problems that would considerably reduce the performance of the system. In addition, it is important to design the air ducts in such a way that the compressed air pressure drop is as low as possible, so that the compression ratio of the compressor is as low as possible and the compressed air is at the lowest possible level of the compressor is the minimum required and, with it, the power consumed by the compressor [27].

2.2.4.3.4 Electric motors

2.2.4.3.4.1 Use of high-performance motors

In the European Community, motor manufacturers, together with the Directorate General for Energy DGXVII, sign a voluntary agreement where they commit themselves to manufacture only motors with improved efficiency and high efficiency. This voluntary agreement came into force in 2000 and its scope of application was IEC 60034 standard motors, with power ratings between 1,1-90kW for 2 and 4 poles with rated voltage 400V 50Hz. In this agreement, motors are classified into three efficiency categories IE1 (High Efficiency), IE2 (Improved Efficiency) and IE3 (Low Efficiency).

Subsequently this regulation has been updated and the last one was approved in 2019, coming into force on 1 July 2021. The new regulation has a broader scope and covers single speed, 50Hz, 60 Hz or 50/60Hz, induction motors with the following characteristics:

- 2 to 8 poles
- Single phase or three phase
- rated output between 0.12kW and 1000kW
- rated voltage from 50V to 1000V
- rated on the basis of continuous duty operation and direct on-line operation

Figure 13. IE classification by the IEC 60034-30-1, 2014.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

When designing and manufacturing high-efficiency motors, special care is taken to reduce the losses in the motor, but as a consequence, the cost of such motors is increased, as higher quality materials, larger stators, more copper in the windings, special bearings, higher quality steel, new component designs, etc. are used in their manufacture.

However, the use of a high efficiency motor, compared to a standard efficiency motor, is much more economically and technically attractive. The higher investment cost is offset by a lower rate of return on investment.

2.2.4.3.4.2 Installation of variable frequency drives

Most industrial pumps, compressors and fans operate at constant speed. This makes it necessary to adjust the flow rate supplied by this equipment by artificially increasing the system losses, by means of a throttling device, which is usually a control or adjustment valve in pumping applications or draught control grilles in ventilation. Systems that do not use a variable frequency drive to regulate pressure or flow rate have losses of between 40% and 80% of the energy consumed. The variable frequency drive allows substantial benefits to be obtained from the speed-power ratio in this type of application. By adjusting the motor speed, the power consumed is considerably reduced (just by reducing the motor speed by 25%, the power consumed is reduced by 57%) [35].

These losses could be avoided by leaving the throttling devices fully open (or eliminating them) and using an AC drive (induction motor) with variable speed to adjust the operating capacity.

2.2.4.4 Energy management

The only way to monitor energy performance is through indicators. For this, it is essential to define beforehand what is going to be measured, how it is going to be measured and how often it is going to be carried out. It is called an energy management system. This energy system is the combination of interrelated or interacting elements of an organisation to establish an energy policy and objectives and to achieve these objectives.

The energy management is based on the continuous improvement cycle, also called the Deming wheel: Plan-Do-Check-Act and aims to [36]:

- Develop a policy for a more efficient use of energy.
- Set targets to meet the policy.
- Use data to better understand and make decisions about energy use and consumption.
- Measure results.
- Review the effectiveness of the policy.
- Continuously improve energy management.

2.3 Renewable energies

Once the processes have been optimised to the maximum, the energy used might come from renewable sources in order to achieve environmentally sustainable transformations. Even though the adoption of renewable energies is always beneficial from the environmental point of view, it is important to reduce consumption first through energy efficiency measures and then using renewable energy sources to supply the required energy so efforts required to implement these RES are minimised. By doing so, power plant's dimensions can be reduced and so the installation's cost (in case of building a power plant) or the energy bill (in case of energy purchase).

2.3.1 Energy generation from renewable sources

In this section, different renewable sources used to obtain energy are presented. These are:

- i) Photovoltaic
- ii) Wind
- iii) Biomass
- iv) Hydraulic energy
- v) Solar thermal
- vi) Biogas
- vii) Combined solutions

viii) Hydrogen

Despite the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic, renewable energy set a record in new power capacity in 2020 and was the only source of electricity generation to register a net increase in total capacity. Investment in renewable power capacity rose, although slightly, for the third consecutive year, and corporations continued to break records for sourcing renewable electricity. Installed renewable power capacity grew by more than 256 gigawatts (GW) during the pandemic, the largest ever increase.

China again led the world in renewable capacity added, accounting for nearly half of all installations in 2020 and leading the global markets for concentrating solar thermal power (CSP), hydropower, solar PV and wind power.

Overall, 2020 was an important milestone for climate change policy, many countries' greenhouse gas targets for the year expired. Countries set new targets, and many committed to carbon neutrality.

Here are some facts about market and industry trends:

- Modern bioenergy provided 5.1% of total global final energy demand in 2019, accounting for around half of all renewable energy in final energy consumption.
- Geothermal electricity generation totalled around 97 TWh in 2020, while direct use of geothermal heat reached about 128 TWh.
- The global hydropower market grew in 2020, but China was responsible for more than half of capacity additions.
- Ocean power represented the smallest portion of the renewable energy market, yet new targets for ocean power capacity were set during the year.
- Solar PV had another record-breaking year, adding as much as an estimated 139 GW, for an estimated total of 760 GW.
- Despite declining costs, concentrating solar thermal power capacity grew in only one country during 2020.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

- An estimated 25.2 gigawatts-thermal (GWth) of new solar thermal capacity was added in 2020, increasing the global total 5% to around 501 GWth.
- The wind power market achieved a record-breaking 93 GW of new installations, bringing total capacity onshore and offshore to nearly 743 GW.

Therefore, the installed capacity in 2020 vs 2019 was as follows:

		2019	2020
INVESTMENT			
New investment (annual) in renewable power and fuels	billion USD	298.4	303.5
POWER			
Renewable power capacity (including hydropower)	GW	2,581.0	2,838.0
Renewable power capacity (not including hydropower)	GW	1,430.0	1,668.0
Hydropower capacity	GW	1,150.0	1,170.0
Solar PV capacity	GW	621.0	760.0
Wind power capacity	GW	650.0	743.0
Bio-power capacity	GW	137.0	145.0
Geothermal power capacity	GW	14.0	14.0
Concentrating solar thermal power (CSP) capacity	GW	6.1	6.2
Ocean power capacity	GW	0.5	0.5
HEAT			
Modern bio-heat demand (estimated)	EJ	13.7	13.9
Solar hot water demand (estimated)	EJ	1.5	1.5
Geothermal direct-use heat demand (estimated)	PJ	421.0	462.0

Table 2. Renewable Energy Indicators 2020. Source: [15]

Additionally, during the last years, there has been a growing interest in wind power, followed by solar energy. New developments, like improved battery technology and offshore solar farms, are expected to speed up renewable growth through 2020. Other renewables, however, are beginning to lag behind like hydroelectric. Its growth has stagnated over the past few years due to increasing criticisms of the environmental impact of hydropower. Many experts also fear climate change may render some river flows too weak or inconsistent to provide significant or reliable power [37].

2.3.1.1 Photovoltaic energy

A Photovoltaic System (PVS) transforms the sunlight into electricity. These systems greatly vary in size, which can be from small rooftop or portable systems to massive utility-scale generation plants, producing up to megawatts. Nowadays, most of the conventional PVSs are connected to the network, whereas the isolated or independent systems only represent a small market portion. In some regions, solar photovoltaic energy is the main renewable energy resource.

The PVS have continuously been improved and they are a mature eco-friendly technology, which presents high yields. Whether the facility has been well-designed and well-maintained, the facility will correctly work having a long operational life. Besides, its costs are continuously decreasing since technology is being enhanced. On the other hand, it is interesting to underline that a PVS has a fast assembly and minimum maintenance requirements, although it has to be periodically revised to ensure its correct performance and, also, the part of panels exposed to the sun has to be cleaned. It is worth mentioning that even on a cloudy day, the PVS generates electricity, although the yield is lower.

2.3.1.2 Wind energy

The wind power consists of using the airflow, which passes through wind turbines to provide mechanical energy to turn the electrical generators. Wind farms have many individual wind turbines, which are normally connected to the electrical energy transmission grid. The onshore wind energy is an economic, competitive and, generally, a cheaper energy source compared to carbon and gas plants.

On the other hand, there is another kind of wind generation: the offshore wind. In comparison with the onshore wind, this has an advantage over the other one: it has the presence of steadier and stronger wind. Moreover, the visual impact of offshore wind turbines is lower. Nevertheless, construction and maintenance costs are much higher. Small onshore wind farms can either provide electricity to the grids or isolated-grid places. In 2017, the total global installed cumulative small wind capacity was estimated at more than 1.0 GW, being China, Italy, U.S. and U.K. the market leaders in terms of installed units [37].

In order to implement small wind turbines, the building location and the surrounding characteristics take great importance since the investment feasibility will increase as a function of wind intensity. This intensity depends on [38] [39]:

- i) The height, since the wind speed increases with this.
- ii) The location since it is windier in plains and sea vicinity zones. Therefore, the conditions to set up this kind of turbine will be better in isolated constructions, close to the sea, tall zones and without surrounding obstacles which can hamper the wind.

2.3.1.3 Biomass

Bioenergy is renewable energy which comes from biological resources. Biomass is any organic material which accumulates solar light as chemical energy. Several materials such as wood and its residues, straw and other crop wastes, manure, sugarcane and many other by-products from a wide variety of agriculture processes could be used as a biofuel. Hence, biomass is the fuel, and the bioenergy is the energy accumulated into the biomass.

Depending on the water content of the biomass, the chemical energy contained in it could be used in different ways. The most extended valorisation process of dry biomass is the direct combustion (exothermic reaction). Besides, there are ways to obtain energy products from dry biomass, these are by gasification or pyrolysis processes. These technologies seek the thermal degradation of organic matter in the absence of oxygen. Instead, other vector gases can be used, such as hydrogen or steam. With these processes, different products could be obtained, among them, syngas, a very appreciated gas used in a lot of applications, like hydrogen extraction for clean energy production.

2.3.1.4 Biogas

On the other hand, for biomass with high moisture content, it is possible to obtain energy products, like biomethane, through anaerobic digestion. Anaerobic digestion is a sequence of processes by which microorganisms break down biodegradable material in the absence of oxygen. The main products of this process are biogas and a liquid digestate.

Biogas is an ideal renewable energy source. Anaerobic digestion of industrial, agricultural, and livestock wastes and sewage sludge mainly produce it. Biogas is mainly composed of CH₄ (around 60%) and CO₂ (around 40%). Because of its methane content, biogas has an important calorific value. The main way of using biogas is through biogas boilers for the recovery of thermal energy. It is usually used to meet the heat needs of the facility in which it is generated.

However, the combustion of the biogas can be carried out in a CHP (Combined Heat and Power or cogeneration) engine, in which thermal but also electric energy is generated. This could be employed to satisfy plants' energy demands or it could be injected to the grid. In addition, biogas could be upgraded to biomethane, through several technologies, to be recovered as biofuel for vehicles or injected into the natural gas network.

2.3.1.5 Hydraulic energy

Hydropower is the energy derived from potential energy. This kind of renewable energy has been used from ancient times by different sorts of water mills for both irrigation and the operation of several mechanical devices. The hydroelectric plants can be categorised in two types: big plants, those providing more than 10 MW; and small plants (< 10 MW). The small independent hydroelectric plants provide around 115 MW around the world [39].

There is another kind of hydraulic energy, which is linked to the water movements in oceans and seas and presents a huge potential of kinetic energy: tidal power stations. Tidal energy is renewable energy generated by sea waves, tides, salinity, and the temperature differences in the ocean, which can be harnessed to produce electricity.

2.3.1.6 Solar thermal energy

Solar thermal energy is the technology which takes advantage of solar energy to generate thermal or electrical energy. Its collectors are classified depending on the temperature as high, medium and low. Low-temperature collectors are not generally glazed, being used to warm both swimming pools and ventilation air. Medium-temperature collectors are similar to low-temperatures ones, but they are used to warm water and air in residences and stores.

Finally, the high-temperature collectors concentrate solar light employing mirrors or lens, achieving temperatures up to 700°C [39]. These are used in industries and to produce electricity.

This kind of energy generation presents a high yield thanks to the wide number of sun hours the whole year in southern Europe. However, there are periods of times where the solar radiation is low and there is no energy production. For this reason, this sort of energy generation normally has a support system [40]. If this system is based on renewable sources, for instance, a biomass boiler, it would be able to generate hot water for sanitary use and heating under the most efficient way, almost without emissions and reducing the primary energy consumption [41]. Whether the installation has been well-designed and well-maintained, it will correctly work, having a long service life. Besides all of this, its feasibility is guaranteed due to the installation costs being not too high.

2.3.1.7 Combined solutions

Today, it is possible to combine several technologies to generate electricity, even mixing conventional techniques, which use fossil sources, and renewable ones. These combinations can be integrated into micro-grids or smart networks. Usually, photovoltaic or wind systems are combined with power generators, especially if there is no network connection. This is because they are cheaper and cheaper since, for instance, the watts per hour price from renewable systems is currently lower compared to that one coming from power generators [42].

The addition of power generators is due to fluctuations of natural resources or unexpected consumptions. However, it is remarkable that a hybrid solution based on renewable sources is virtually independent of fossil fuels problems like its variable costs due to, for instance, political decisions. On the other hand, integrated batteries in wind turbines can enable short-term energy storage, reducing costs, and increasing the reliability and yield [43].

2.3.1.8 Hydrogen

Hydrogen is one of the very few options for storing electricity over days, weeks or months. Today hydrogen is mainly used in the refining and chemical sectors and it is produced from fossil fuels, accounting for 6% of global natural gas use and 2% of coal consumption and being responsible for 830 MtCO₂ of annual CO₂ emissions. At the moment, hydrogen is an object of great interest in the energy sector, a large number of projects exist in which “green hydrogen” (hydrogen produced through electrolysis, using water and renewable energies) is produced. Scale-up will be critical to bring down the costs of technologies for producing and using clean hydrogen, such as electrolyzers, fuel cells and hydrogen production with CCUS [44].

2.3.2 Renewable energies in the agricultural sector

Almost all of previously mentioned renewable energies can be applied in agriculture:

There are some projects in which special PV panels that allow solar radiation required by plants to pass through or even floating PV installations on agricultural water reservoirs, reducing water evaporation while producing energy. These approaches, in which energy generation and agriculture coexist are of great importance, as one of the main social issues that exist today when a new solar farm is projected is precisely the opposition from part of the society that claims that agriculture is being displaced by solar energy installations. Besides, it would even be possible to generate more energy than it is consumed by the farmer, who would be able to sell it and receive an additional income from agriculture.

The production of hot water using solar thermal systems to rise the temperature in greenhouses is also used in some cases [45]. This thermal use of solar energy is especially relevant due to the high cost for which heating greenhouses in winter accounts for (around 70% of the total production cost) [46], being possible to use this thermal energy in solar dryers.

Eolic energy can be of great interest when the required distances and wind speeds can be reached, but this is not always possible. The minimum speed for small wind turbines to start

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

rotating is around 2 m/s, at 3.5 m/s turbines start generating electricity, while the speed for max power generation is between 10 and 15 m/s. Spacing between turbines because of the length of blades and the effect on the wind must be kept: a usual rule-of-thumb is spacing turbines around 7 rotor diameters away from each other. In this case, the application would be entirely related to energy use.

Biomass is a kind of energy that fits perfectly with agriculture, since due to its activity an important amount of wood and other organic residues is produced. These residues can be valorized in thermal applications or even used to generate biogas in bio-reactors. Some applications include the production of biogas, biomethane or biohydrogen. However, in the A2C project, the organic waste will be used for the production of bioplastics and valuable extracts instead.

Hydraulic energy is not always available, since it requires an available water source from which energy can be obtained. In agriculture, using microturbines would be possible to recover energy from the tubes when using gravity-fed systems [47], but the energy produced would be negligible. In most cases it would not be wise to implement these devices in pumped-systems, as energy is transformed from pressure energy to kinetic energy and then electrical energy, losing part of it in the process. As a result, generated energy would be lower than the one consumed in pumps. This system would only be an option in those cases in which a higher pressure is required for some initial points of the water grid, remaining higher pressure than required in later points, thus installing these microturbines.

Finally, hydrogen can be produced by using an electrolyser and then used to generate heat or electricity, but this would only make sense if storing energy is required, since energy is needed to produce hydrogen, and there are efficiency losses both during the production of hydrogen and during its transformation in heat electricity. Heat can be produced burning hydrogen, while electricity can be produced using a fuel cell, which is an electrochemical device in which hydrogen reacts with oxygen to produce water and electricity. In some cases, usable heat can be produced too by these devices. Hydrogen is an interesting option for energy storage when long-time solutions are required since, unlike batteries, no energy loss through time is experienced in hydrogen systems. Besides, once a hydrogen storage

solution is implemented, little extra area is required to significantly increase storage capacity. However, the required investment associated with hydrogen technology is still high due to its low maturity and when compressed hydrogen storing solutions are adopted, a relevant part of energy is consumed in compressors.

2.3.3 A2C processes implementation

In this section different green technologies for in-situ renewable energy generation, and the viability of its implementation are presented. Some of these technologies like wind and solar energy can be applied without emitting pollutants or exhausting gas into the atmosphere since they are environmentally friendly and pollution-free energy sources.

2.3.3.1 Solar photovoltaic power

Solar photovoltaic power generation, which has the remarkable advantages of cleanness, high efficiency, safety, and renderability, has become one of the environmentally friendly alternative energy sources [48].

On the other hand, this energy generation has also social-economic advantages like easy installation, little maintenance requirements, a long-life service, high resistance to extreme climatology conditions, it is independent of fossil fuels producer countries, it can be implemented in those non-interconnected zones (NIZ), and the production can be increased in a modulate way and sold to the grid.

Solar energy can be used to pump water or treat wastewaters. This energy can also be directly utilised to any processes. In general, it could be employed in any electric-consumption treatment system. Despite all these advantages, the intermittence of this power source is an important drawback to deal with.

The most direct solution is to accumulate the energy generated in the hours of the day with the most radiation in batteries, for later consumption at night. Nevertheless, this increases the investment costs. An alternative could be, for instance, taking advantage of the “net balance” option, which involves pouring into the grid at production hours, and consuming it when self-produced energy is not available. New legislation has been developed and it

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

drives the self-consumption conditions, making this option a very interesting one since the end-user is not obliged to become an enterprise and can be a producer at the same time. In this way, bureaucracy, and other procedures to be grid-connected are avoided.

A photovoltaic system can produce up to 95% of the net renewable energy whether the installation has been well-maintained. On the other hand, the amortisation period varies from 5 to 10 years (currently closer to 5 years) depending on several parameters like components quality, suitable installation, good consumption estimations, etc [49] [50] [51]. Figure 5 displays the photovoltaic energy costs as a function of time, which are more and more profitable.

Figure 14. Photovoltaic installation costs as a function of time. Source: [52]

2.3.3.2 Wind power

It is true that wind energy distribution has certain limitations. However, it is a widely distributed energy source compared to other renewable energies [48]. The wind turbines need speed wind between 5 and 6 m/s, on average, to be competitive. The produced energy can be stored in batteries and supply it to any process that consumes electricity [53]. This renewable energy could be applied in any A2C process that requires electricity, including extrusion processes, heating in chemical or biochemical reactors, pumping, microwave or ultrasound equipment, etc.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

In small facilities, wind energy installations use wind generators able to produce less than 100 kW and, thus, it would be necessary to perform a wind speed study, economic feasibility study, and cost-benefit analysis before implementing this technology. It is mandatory to mention that wind power technology has been improved and it is nowadays more and more efficient and cheaper. Figure 15 and Figure 16 show the wind onshore and offshore costs as a function of time.

Figure 15. Wind onshore installation costs as a function of time. Source: [52]

Figure 16. Wind offshore installation costs as a function of time. Source: [52]

2.3.3.3 Biomass

The most extended use of biomass (mainly agricultural wastes) is as an energy source to produce thermal energy through its combustion in a biomass boiler.

The mentioned technology is similar to boilers which use fossil fuels. But, in this case, it is considered that the CO₂ emissions are null. Pellets are cheaper than fossil fuels like propane and diesel, being this relationship that determines its amortisation. Biomass has a less calorific value than fossil fuels and, thus, it is necessary a larger volume of biomass to obtain the same energy quantity. As for the disadvantages, some boilers cannot use unprocessed biomass and it has to be installed in a place only allocated for it. Whether the installation is well-maintained, its minimum life of service should be between 20 and 25 years.

Figure 17 shows bioenergy costs as a function of time. It can be observed that the trend of the prices is increasing and, thus, for a treatment plant the operating costs depend on its integration with other treatment processes. This is the reason why this technology is not usually employed.

Figure 17. Biomass installation costs as a function of time. Source: [52]

Biomass could be applied in those processes of the A2C project that require heat, such as those including bioreactors or fermentors (these processes usually take place at temperatures around 50°C) or extrusion processes in which polymers need to be heated to flow through the opening of the extruder.

2.3.3.4 Solar thermal power

The yield of solar thermal energy is not constant because the energy of the sun is variable. Another point to consider is the maintenance of this kind of installation since if this is not correct, the panels yield is considerably reduced. Thus, it is recommendable to clean them at least every 6 months, besides a periodical review of pipes, valves, etc.

As previously mentioned, and keeping in mind that every particular case is different, the installation has a minimal life of service of 20 years, which allows amortising the facility in a short time; between 5 and 10 years. Figure 18 shows the solar thermal energy costs as a function of time, which are clearly above other renewable sources.

Figure 18. Solar thermal installation costs as a function of time. Source: [52]

Just like biomass, solar thermal energy could be applied in those processes of the A2C project that require heat, such as those including bioreactors, fermentors or extruders.

2.3.3.5 Biogas

Biogas is a renewable gas composed mainly of methane and carbon dioxide obtained from the anaerobic degradation -without oxygen- of organic waste.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

It therefore involves the transformation of livestock and agro-industrial waste and sludge from water treatment plants, which are closely related to the objective of this project. The waste thus becomes the raw material for an energy source. This is its renewable character. Just as plastics accumulated in a landfill can be recycled and turned into new products, here pig slurry is transformed into energy [54].

Biogas could be used to produce heat or electricity for the previously described processes of the A2C project. However, as this biogas is often produced from agricultural waste, and the aim of this project is precisely to produce new products using that waste, biogas is not considered to be the best option.

2.3.3.6 Hybrid systems

Today, hybrid systems are also more and more attractive, above all those independent remote systems. These hybrid systems can be a combination of photovoltaic system, a wind turbine with or without a support generator, and battery storage. As for the disadvantages, both wind and sunshine intensity constantly vary with weather and climate. However, the use of wind and solar energy has been improved thanks to the breakthroughs in technology. The comprehensive utilisation of both kinds of energies establishes a more stable, reliable, and economical energy system in many aspects [48].

2.3.3.7 Hydrogen

One solution for the utilisation of renewable energy could be the use of hydrogen. This gas, if it is produced by electrolysis with energy from renewable sources, would be "green hydrogen" and could be used as an energy vector to adapt the energy demand of the processes to the production of renewable energies, which, as mentioned above, are variable over time. Through this technology, during the hours of peak production of renewable energy demand, the energy would be transformed by an electrolyser into hydrogen with water as the only input. This hydrogen would be stored in tanks designed for this purpose and when the energy demand of the process exceeds that of renewable energy production, it would be transformed back into electricity by means of a fuel cell without the emission of any

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

greenhouse gases, only water vapour would be emitted. In other words, hydrogen would act as a battery, or rather as an energy vector.

Hydrogen could be used for both electricity and heat production in the project, with all applications previously mentioned. However, energy is lost in the transformation from electricity to hydrogen and the later transformation from hydrogen to electricity or heat. Besides, the main problem with this sustainable alternative is the current price of its use, which does not yet make it cost-effective compared to conventional batteries or a PPA of renewable origin. As a result, hydrogen is not considered a good option for the A2C processes.

In summary:

RENEWABLE SOURCE	PROS	CONS
SOLAR	This kind of electricity generation does not pollute, non-consumption of fossil fuels, non-generation of residues, it is noiseless, the energy quality is high and it is inexhaustible on a human scale.	The intermittence of this power source is an important drawback to deal with.
WIND	Wind energy is renewable and clean, presents low operating costs and an efficient use of land space.	It is intermittent and requires a wind speed study, it is noisy and provides visual pollution and physical environmental impacts around them.
BIOMASS	Null CO ₂ emissions, pellets are cheaper than fossil fuels. Biogas can satisfy some of the energy demand when it is used in a combined heat-power engine.	It requires a huge volume of biomass to produce the same energy quantity that using fossil fuel due to its lower calorific value. Anaerobic digestion has very high investment costs, causing small and

		medium-sized processing plants to normally not be able to implement this technology.
BIOGAS	Biogas is a simple and low-cost technology that encourages a circular economy. Gas generated through biodigestion is non-polluting.	It would only be feasible if there is a company with organic waste nearby such as WWTPs, food industries etc.
HYDROGEN	It is a very good alternative as a more sustainable use of batteries, as it does not generate any waste and generates adaptability to energy production through renewable energies.	The current price of their production limits their implementation.

Table 3. Pros and cons of renewable sources.

To sum up, different renewable energies are available to be chosen from. Depending on the specific location and requirements of the project, some options may be more appropriate than others. For instance, PV solar energy can be of great help in southern Europe, where there is generally higher solar radiation, but not so much in northern Europe; biogas can be a good choice as long as its price is low or there are available wastes to produce it.

In any case, the implementation of energy efficiency measures and RES help reduce the carbon footprint of any process, be it agricultural or industrial. In agriculture, the use of solar or wind energy to provide electricity to pumps or illumination, the valorization of wood waste to produce biogas, the use of alternative fuel vehicles or the use of solar thermal power to heat greenhouses could reduce its impact on the environment by lowering greenhouse gas emissions. In the A2C project, all these recommendations will be taken into consideration to lower GHG emissions as much as possible. A LCA will be performed in future deliverables, analysing the project's impact on the environment, not only due to energy and water consumption, but also considering subproducts, by-products and final products.

3 Water recommendations

3.1 Water issues related to agriculture

Water is an essential resource in agriculture, both for growing crops and for processing the produce into products. The sector however puts pressure on both water availability and water quality. In Spain, agriculture represents 65% of all water extractions, of which less than 30% is accounted for by ground water. In addition, diffuse pollution from agriculture causes nitrate, pharmaceuticals and pesticides to end up in 34% of surface water bodies and 56% of groundwater bodies [55].

For the region of Murcia specifically, water has been the subject of many debates and disputes. Murcia, a region known for its agriculture, receives water from the Tagus River via a system of pipelines and aqueducts to the Segura River basin. Despite the extra water imported to the region, only 4% of the original runoff of the Segura River reaches its mouth. This increases the risk of desertification, and groundwater levels are falling [56].

Restrictions on the amount of transferred water forces farmers to look for alternative water sources, which are often more expensive, and therefore not feasible. Desalinated water is five times as expensive as water from the aqueduct, and concerns surrounding the mineral content of the water and its effect on crops have been raised. In addition, desalinating water requires about 3kWh per cubic meter, increasing energy consumption and carbon footprint of the water.

Alternatively, the agricultural sector is looking into reuse of water. The European Commission (EC) approved Regulation 2020/741, which describes the minimal requirements for water reuse in agriculture. This regulation is in effect since June 2023, and opens the road to the use of treated wastewater for irrigation [57]. The implementation for this way of reuse however requires extensive infrastructure, which comes at high investment costs. . In addition, water treatment comes at higher cost and energy consumption compared to using freshwater, which slows its implementation for irrigation use. Hristov et al. investigated the potential of reusing treated wastewater for irrigation in a European context [58]. The average potential reduction of freshwater use was 14%, where Belgium has the

highest potential at 35% and Czech Republic the lowest, around 1%. This simulation however is only the potential reuse, the actual situation is far from the calculated potential.

Finding a solution or alternative source for irrigation water is out of scope of the A2C project. However, the project deals with treatment of water streams in the processing and packaging of agricultural products. Reducing the intake of water for such processes, either by smart process design or reuse of water streams, also reduces the pressure on water sources in an area already affected by water scarcity.

3.2 Water in the circular economy

Water is one of the most essential resources on earth, as it is essential to survival of all life. For humans, water is very important in many sectors, such as industry, agriculture, heating, cooling and other sectors. Although the amount of water on our planet stays the same and is considered renewable because it circulates through the water cycle, in recent years shortage of fresh water is an emerging problem [59]. Therefore, water has to be treated as a valuable resource, and plays a large role in the circular economy [60].

The circularity of water has been incorporated in several of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as presented by the United Nations in 2015 [61]. Goals such as moving towards sustainable agriculture, availability of clean water, preserving aquatic environments worldwide and the sustainability of production processes and tourism all require a different approach to how we use and dispose our water.

Goals such as moving towards sustainable agriculture, availability of clean water, preserving aquatic environments worldwide and the sustainability of production processes and tourism all require a different approach to how we use and dispose of our water.

Within Europe, water management over the past 30 years has moved towards sustainable use of water, which is apparent from adopting EU legislation such as the Drinking Water Directive [62], the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive [63] and the Water Framework Directive [64]. These legal acts ensure the drive to improve the status of water within the EU.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

To ensure the availability of fresh water for this generation but also for the future, it has to be incorporated in a circular model. Circularity does not only include the reuse of the water, but also reusing the substances in the water, to ensure a near zero discharge of materials into the environment. The A2C project embodies this view by aiming to integrate all the waste streams from the Murcia region into a circular model. Not only the waste streams from agriculture are changed into resources for new and sustainable materials (bioplastics, components for cosmetics etc.), but the water streams in the accompanying processes are also considered.

When considering the circularity of water in particular, it is worth mentioning that the water has to be treated to be suitable for the purpose it is required for. In addition, the availability of water within the Region that will be used again, contributes to the self-sufficiency of the region. When designing a suitable system for water reuse, both the fit-for-purpose treatment and the self-sufficiency have to be taken into account.

Smol, Adam and Preisner state that in waste management, some methods that prevent the loss of water are already implemented, and can be classified according to the following list [65]:

- 2Rs: reduction and reuse,
- 3Rs: reduction, reuse and recycling,
- 4Rs: reduction, reuse, recycling and recovery.

Reduce encompasses all processes that prevent the generation of wastewater, including reducing the use of water. Reducing the intake of fresh water reduces the pressure on fresh water availability, and also reduces the amount of pollution that might be spilled into the environment.

Reuse can further release the pressure on fresh water supplies. Any water that can be reused in for instance production processes prevents the use of potable water for non-potable purposes. Within the A2C project, it is viable to consider the exchange of water streams between processes, if the proper treatment steps allow this reuse.

Recycling is the reclamation of potable water from wastewater. It has to be noted however that this strategy often comes with high costs, and should only be considered if the wastewater cannot be reused in other processes. Recycling of water requires advanced technologies such as membrane filtration, which is able to remove most pollutants.

Recovery is the strategy that is most related to the A2C project. By treating the pollutants in the water not as a problem but as resources for instance fertilizers, biopolymers and cosmetics, value is added to the wastewater.

Smol et al. included two more additional aspects to the circular model presented above, which are:

Reclamation, which focuses specifically on the removal of pollutants in the water. In the past years, micropollutants such as medicines, crop protection agents and microplastics reduce the quality of surface water. In the A2C project, considering those possible threats to the water streams involved will have to be taken into account.

Rethink is, according to Smol et al, the most important aspect to move towards a circular model. Implementing a circular model effectively requires a change in mentality from 'take, make, waste' towards 'reduce, reuse, recycle, recover'. This will require the cooperation of many partners, and a new way of thinking for society. A2C is an example of rethinking, not only for water, but for agricultural waste as a whole.

3.3 Description of Agro2Circular processes

The main waste streams identified in the Agro2Circular project are fruit and vegetable waste, and agricultural plastics such as greenhouse and ground covering films, and post-industrial multilayer plastics. In a circular model, these streams will be treated to recover valuable compounds, and what waste is left will be recycled in other processes. In the following sections, an overview is given of the proposed routes and processes in the Agro2Circular project. The largest water streams which are suitable for reuse will be identified, and possible treatment technologies will be proposed.

3.3.1 Process descriptions: Agrifood wastes treatment

The agrifood waste treatment will be done primarily by CNTC. The processes involved are:

- Agrifood waste classification and conditioning.
- Green solvent+ultrasounds assisted extraction of high value substances from agrifood waste.
- Green solvent+enzymatic hydrolysis assisted extraction (EAE)+microwaves assisted extraction (MAE) of high value substances from agrifood waste.
- Purification and conservation of the high value substances.
- Stabilisation and conservation of the high value substances.

In these processes, no large waste streams suitable for treatment and reuse have been identified. Therefore, for the rest of the report, these processes will be left out of the discussion.

3.3.2 Process descriptions: Multilayer plastic waste treatment

The recycling of packaging materials will be performed by a chain of Agro2Circular partners. These can be summarised as:

- Preliminary decontamination of the multilayer films (Green World Compounding).
- Optical sorting (Iris technology).
- Separation of aluminium from the complex multilayer films (Saperatec).
- Enzymatic recycling of PE and PET (Epoch Biodesign).
- Aluminium recycling (Universität für Bodenkultur).
- Production of building blocks from TPA, EG and alkenes resulting from the enzymatic recycling (University of Milano-Bicocca).
- Production of PHBV and carotenoids (Centro Tecnológico del Calzado y del Plástico, Universidad de Alicante).

In this chain, multiple wastewater suitable for treatment have been identified. The preliminary decontamination of multilayer plastics, as performed by Green World Compounding, consumes large amounts of water. At this moment, the washing water of agricultural films is treated (although minimally) and recycled into the washing line, tap water has to be taken in regularly to compensate for water losses. The waste water from post-industrial multilayer plastics will have different characteristics from the agricultural films because the pollutants are different, so it will also require a new treatment approach. Another consideration in treating this waste stream before either reuse or eventual release into the sewer is the formation of microplastics during the grinding and washing. Microplastics are a pollutant of emerging concern, as they can be found in the air, water and soil, and even in human blood [66]. Their effects on the environment and our health is not fully understood, and therefore release into the environment should be limited as much as possible.

The second waste stream that has been identified for treatment is the salty supernatant from the PHBV and carotenoid production. These compounds are produced by halophilic organisms in a highly saline broth, and after fermentation a large waste stream containing salts, organic residues and possibly other compounds is left. Treatment of this waste stream serves a double purpose: recovering the salts for reuse in PHBV production, and separating off the organic compounds which interfere with the growth of PHBV producing bacteria.

The third water stream identified is the broth after enzymatic recycling. This stream might not be as large in volume as the previously described waste streams, but the high value compounds produced justify a treatment process. In this waste stream, the monomers terephthalic acid (TPA) and ethylene glycol (EG) will have to be separated from the broth containing the enzymes and plastics. The enzymes and plastics can be reintroduced in the process, and the monomers can be used in other applications.

3.4 Recommendations

3.4.1 Methodology

In order to give recommendations for the three relevant water streams mentioned in section 8.2.2 it is essential to understand the process in which the water was used and which pollutants can be expected. Furthermore, it is important to understand what the purity of the

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

separated stream should be for its intended reuse. This is not only relevant for the water, but also for the recovered salts and monomers.

The global strategy for determining the most suitable water treatment technology for each of the three defined streams can be summarized as:

- Collecting detailed information on the process in which the waste water stream is produced. At least the following information is required:
 - A description of the process (for instance, plastic washing and shredding) and the water streams involved in the process
 - Quality and quantity of the water that is taken into the process (tap water, reused water with certain requirements etc)
 - Quality and quantity of the effluent of the process, including analytical results of the components in the water
 - An overview of the water treatment systems already in place, and the efficiencies of those treatments.

After the information is collected, analyzed and summarized, a strategy for treatment of the waste water stream can be formulated. To find the most suitable technology, multiple boundary conditions have to be taken into account:

- The prioritized recovered stream: this can be either the water, or the compounds in the water (such as salts or monomers)
- The required quality of the recovered stream (water, salts or monomers) for its intended use
- Identification of additional opportunities for resource recovery, if any
- Production of additional waste streams, such as regeneration liquids,
- Possible risks of accumulation of harmful substances in either the recovered stream or the waste stream (such as microplastics, heavy metals etc)
- Any additional boundary conditions dictated by the specific process or waste water stream.

Based on this information and boundary conditions, possible treatment technologies can be identified. The performance of the technology however has to be tested in practice, which will be done in WP3, WP5 and WP6.

3.4.2 Available treatment technologies

The most suitable technology to treat a water stream depends on many factors, such as which pollutants are present, to what standard that water has to be polished for reuse and if a recovery stream is desirable. In this chapter, a first overview is presented of water treatment technologies that can be of value in recovering water and resources in the Agro2Circular processes. The list included in this deliverable contains well-established technologies, but also state-of-the-art technologies

It must be noted that regular microbial water treatment (the common treatment technology used in for instance Wastewater Treatment Plants - WWTP) was not included in this list. This was done because the organic components in the wastewater will be used for the production of bioplastics or other resources instead of being removed by conventional treatment.

In the following sections, a short overview and description of each technology will be given. The suitability for different pollutants and limitations will be described.

3.4.2.1 Flotation/sedimentation

Flotation and sedimentation can be done in one treatment step. When water with particles is left over time, heavy particles (such as soil) will slowly sink to the bottom of the tank, whereas light particles (such as oil and grease) will float to the top of the tank (Figure 10).

In WWTPs the scum layer on top is scraped off the surface and disposed of. The sludge layer on the bottom is transported out of the tank via belts or a collection hopper system, depending on how the flotation/sedimentation tank was designed.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

The removal efficiency of flotation and sedimentation depends on several factors, such as the density difference between the particles and the water, and particle size and shape.

Flotation can be enhanced by introducing air bubbles in a dissolved air flotation system (DAF). Light particles adhere to the bubble surface, and are transported upwards to the scum layer. Sedimentation can be enhanced by using inclined plate settlers. In these sedimentation basins, plates are placed under an angle, aiding the settling of heavier particles in a shorter time.

Figure 19. A schematic representation of flocculation and sedimentation. Source: [67]

3.4.2.2 Coagulation and flocculation

Small particles, and particles with a density very similar to water, will not be removed by flotation or sedimentation. This often happens with clay particles, microplastics, very small oil droplets and fine organic material. They often have a surface charge, which causes the particles to repel each other, creating a stable suspension. Therefore, a coagulant can be added to the water, which overcomes the surface charge of the particles and destabilised the suspension. The coagulant is often added in a quick mixing process, after which the flocculation step starts. Flocculation is done by gently stirring the solution, and allows the destabilised particles to clump together in larger particles that can settle (Figure 20).

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

Figure 20. A schematic representation of the process of coagulation. Source: [68]

Coagulation and flocculation together with flotation and sedimentation can remove most solids from the water, but requires adding chemicals to the water. These coagulants are often expensive, and are mostly made of polymers, which are sometimes classified as microplastics themselves. Iron- and aluminium based coagulants add metals to the sludge, which can cause problems in sludge disposal or reuse. Biodegradable polymeric coagulants are emerging in the market, but do not always reach the desired removal efficiency.

A more recent development is electrocoagulation, in which metal ions are dosed to the water by a reactive anode. This technology can only be applied in water streams with sufficient conductivity, but possesses a few advantages over traditional coagulation. The coagulant can be dosed more accurately and in lower doses, the formed gasses at the electrodes provide flotation, and the produced sludge is often lower in volume compared to traditional coagulation and flocculation.

3.4.2.3 Hydrocyclones

Hydrocyclones use a vortex to separate heavy particles from a liquid flow. The vortex is created in a cylindrical or conical container, and the water is injected at high speed at the top of the container (Figure 21).

Gravitational and centrifugal effects pull the heavier particles outwards and downwards, where the speed increases because of the tapered shape. This further increases the separation. The heavy particles leave the hydrocyclone via the apex at the bottom. The water exits through the central vortex in a fast rotating upward motion, and leaves the cyclone via the overflow.

Hydrocyclones are relatively cost efficient, as they require a pump and a static container. Because cyclones do not contain any moving parts, they require less maintenance compared to more complex systems.

Figure 21. A schematic representation of the flows in a hydrocyclone. Source: [73]

3.4.2.4 Filtration and membranes

Filtration is a separation technology based on size exclusion. Particles that are larger than the holes in the filter are retained, whereas smaller particles and the fluid pass through the filter. Filters can take the shape of coarse sieves or plates for large particles. For smaller particles however, depth filters are often used, which depend on a porous medium rather than a porous surface. The macroporous internal structure of the layer is able to retain small particles effectively, because they are trapped in the internal structure of the filter. Depth filters are able to retain particles down to about 1 μm in size, such as some bacteria, cells and other microorganisms (Figure 22).

Figure 22. An overview of particles rejected by different classes of membranes. Source: [69]

For particles below 1 μm , filters are not sufficient anymore and membranes are used. Membranes are thin semi-permeable layers that can be tailored to the specific separation process that is desired. Membranes can be operated in the dead-end or crossflow mode, where the latter is applied in continuous processes most often. A pressure is applied across the membrane, which allows the passing of all particles that are smaller than the pore size of the membrane (the permeate) whereas the particles that are larger than the membrane Pores are concentrated on the feed side (the retentate or concentrate). Membranes are usually subdivided into four classes (Figure 23).

Figure 23. An overview of rejected substances by different membrane classes. Source: [70]

Microfiltration (MF) is capable of filtering out bacteria and suspended solids, but other particles and ions will pass through the membrane. Ultrafiltration (UF) will also retain viruses, and nanofiltration (NF) is capable of removing multivalent ions from the feed stream. The most selective class of membranes, reverse osmosis (RO), consists of very dense membranes that only allow the passage of water molecules.

Membrane separation is an efficient method of purifying and concentrating a wide range of streams, but various factors have to be taken into account. The membrane material has to be suitable and resilient for the feed stream. It is also important to determine what particles will have to be removed, as smaller pore sizes are associated with higher applied pressures and higher energy consumption.

Finally, all membranes suffer from fouling. During filtration, particles will get stuck on the membrane surface and in the pores, reducing the permeate flow and with that increasing the pressure and energy required. To remediate this, the membrane has to be backwashed and cleaned regularly, which can be included in an automated membrane operation

program. At some point however, a membrane module might have to be replaced if too much irreversible fouling has occurred.

3.4.2.5 Electrodialysis

Electrodialysis (ED) utilises ion exchange membranes in combination with an electric field to remove salt ions from a dilute feed solution. An ED cell consists of a stack of anion and cation exchange membranes, which only let ions of either negative or positive charge pass. On either side of the stack, an anode and cathode is placed to create the electrical field and facilitate the transport of electrons (Figure 24).

Courtesy EET Corporation
www.eetcorp.com

Figure 24. A schematic overview of an electrodialysis stack, showing the movement of ions over the membranes and the half-reactions at the electrodes. Source: [71]

The feed stream and concentrate stream are fed into the cell alternating between successive compartments. Under the influence of the electric field, the cations in the feed stream pass

through the cationic exchange membranes, and the anions in the feed stream pass through the anionic exchange membranes. The anions end up in the concentrate stream, so the salinity of the feed stream is decreased, while the salinity of the concentrated stream is increased. To ensure charge neutrality, half reactions take place at the electrodes, and electrons pass through the electrical circuit connecting both ends of the cell. ED is different from for instance reverse osmosis, because the ions are removed from the feed stream rather than retained in the retentate stream. In addition, with ED it is possible to work in for higher salt concentrations than is possible with RO. The feed recovery of ED is usually also higher than that of RO, as not the water, but the ions are moved across the membrane.

3.4.2.6 Membrane distillation

Membrane distillation depends on the difference in vapor pressure between the feed and permeate side of a membrane. The membranes used in membrane distillation are hydrophobic, and only allow water vapor to pass, and no liquid water. The feed side of the membrane is fed with a hot feed stream, whereas the permeate side is either fed with a cool permeate stream. In other configurations, the permeate side of the membrane consists of an air gap with a cool surface behind, increasing the thermal isolation between feed and permeate side and increasing the efficiency of the cell (Figure 25).

Figure 25. Schematic representation of membrane distillation. Source: [72]

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

The water in the hot feed stream evaporates into the pores of the membrane, passes through to the permeate side and condenses on the cool surface or liquid stream. The feed stream becomes concentrated, and pure water is recovered. Membrane distillation can be performed using different configurations, for instance using vacuum or a gas stream on the permeate side of the membrane. Membrane distillation is often used for desalination of seawater or brackish water.

3.4.2.7 Adsorption

Adsorption is often done by passing the feed flow over a bed of adsorbing material, such as sand, granulated activated carbon (GAC), or ion exchange resins. Pollutants in the feed stream adsorb to the filter material, resulting in clean water. The adsorbing material is chosen based on the pollutants that have to be removed.

Sand filters are very efficient in removing particles and microorganisms. Sand filters can be operated as quick sand filters, where the water is pushed through under pressure. Slow or gravity fed sand filters allow the water to trickle down. Slow sand filters are usually colonised by microorganisms in the top layer, which are able to remove organic pollutants in the water. The permeate flow however is much lower compared to rapid sand filters.

GAC is a porous form of carbon with a very large surface area per volume. It is capable of removing most organics, heavy metals and some ions from the water stream. It is also commonly used to improve the odour and taste of drinking water in countries where the tap water is chlorinated.

Ion exchange resins are commonly used to remove unwanted ions from the water by replacing them with another ion. A common example is the softening of water, where the magnesium and calcium ions are replaced with sodium. Heavy metals can also be removed from water using ion exchange resins.

Although adsorption can be applied to remove a great spectrum of pollutants, the adsorption material will become saturated over time and lose its adsorptive properties. At that point, the material has to be cleaned, replaced or regenerated. The backwashing of a sand filter

therefore creates a waste stream with pollutants, GAC has to be regenerated by either chemical or thermal processes, creating a waste stream or consuming a lot of energy. Ion exchange resins have to be regenerated by flushing the column with brine, which also produces a waste stream.

3.4.3 Preliminary recommendations

Based on the technologies described in the previous section, the boundary conditions as imposed by the processes and the results from tests on lab scale, preliminary recommendations for water treatment were established. In the following sections, the preliminary recommendations are discussed per Agro2Circular process. The processes recommended here will be tested on pilot scale in WP6 – Demonstrators.

3.4.3.1 Plastic washing water

Based on data received from Green World Compounding and additional analysis performed at CEW, the pollutants present in the water were determined. The washing water from post-industrial multilayer plastics is mainly contaminated with fruit leftovers, which results in high organic contamination. The magnitude of contamination depends on the contents of the packaging but also on the time the plastic has been stored, because bacteria present on the plastics consume the organic compounds. The washing water contains microplastics, and possibly also nanoplastics. The goal is to reuse the water for plastic washing, and therefore solid particles have to be removed. For treatment of this water, two possible technologies were selected: ultrafiltration and electrocoagulation. Both were tested in the lab on particle removal. Ultrafiltration was able to remove 99% of all solid particles, whereas electrocoagulation was able to remove 80% of the solid particles. Microplastics removal was confirmed in ultrafiltration. In electrocoagulation, particles were still present in the effluent, but the nature of the particles could not be determined. Detailed results can be found in deliverable D3.2. In WP6, ultrafiltration will be tested on pilot scale, in a feed and bleed configuration. This means the water in the washing line will be treated to conserve water quality, and a small stream of concentrate will be bled from the system. This stream should be concentrated in organics and might be used for PHBV production.

3.4.3.2 Enzyme recovery and monomer separation

The enzymatic PET degradation is performed in a broth, and after the hydrolysis a mixture of buffers, enzyme, crystalline PET and monomers is left. The monomers should be isolated to be used in other processes, whereas the enzyme (if it is still active) can be recycled into the degradation process, together with the broth and leftover plastics. The molecular weight of the monomers is about 70 Da for EG and 200 Da for TPA, whereas the enzyme has a molecular weight of 15 kDa. This difference in molecular weight makes size based separation possible, so ultrafiltration with a molecular weight cutoff of 10 kDa was selected. A small PES membrane cell was used to filter the broth on lab scale, and about 90% of the monomers could be recovered. This waste stream is relatively small and will not be tested on pilot scale, but might be demonstrated in WP6 on a tabletop scale setup.

3.4.3.3 Salt recovery from PHBV fermentation broth

After PHBV production, the biomass is removed from the broth with ultrafiltration. The resulting permeate contains salts, dissolved organic compounds and possibly other nutrients. The goal of the water treatment is to recover the salts for reuse in the fermentation process, without also adding compounds that could hinder the bacterial growth. It has been observed that recycling part of the spent broth to a fresh fermentation batch influences the PHBV production negatively, which might be caused by EPS-like substances in the liquid. To separate the salts from the organic compounds, electrodialysis is an appropriate technology. The fermentation broth will be desalinated, producing a concentrate with high salt concentration, and a product stream with the organic compounds. The product stream can be discarded or used in a different process, and the concentrate with salts can be reused in the PHBV production process. This treatment technology is currently tested in WP5, and will be demonstrated on tabletop scale in WP6.

4 Conclusions

Deliverable 1.7 establishes a set of recommendations on energy efficiency (use of renewable energy technologies and optimisation of key energy parameters) and sustainable water & wastewater management (preliminary water demand, water quality criteria and wastewater characteristics) for the A2C processes and technologies.

These processes are still at a medium TRL level and are therefore not implemented on a large scale. Because of this, the A2C processes are still in the design phase which is the right time to consider all the measures that can be taken to optimise them and make them as energy efficient as possible, which will also have an impact on improving their economic viability.

With regard to energy efficiency, a series of generic recommendations have been described throughout the deliverable, focusing on the reduction of process demand, the need for maintenance and controls once the processes are implemented on a larger scale, the incorporation of the most efficient equipment and the importance of energy monitoring.

Due to the fact that the specific equipment involved in each process was not yet available, generic recommendations have been made for heating, cooling and compressed air equipment, as well as electric motors. Later, once the necessary information has been obtained, specific measures related to energy efficiency will be suggested for each process.

Once the energy efficiency recommendations have been made, as energy use is inevitably necessary in all processes, a number of renewable energy alternatives have been proposed to make the processes sustainable.

The renewable energies described are solar, wind, biomass, biogas, hydroelectric, solar thermal, combination of several and hydrogen, although it is considered that for the processes of the A2C project the most suitable renewable energy sources are those described in Table 3 (solar, wind, biomass, biogas and hydrogen).

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

The two largest water streams in Agro2Circular are produced by the washing of post-industrial multilayer plastic packaging, and by the PHBV production in saline conditions. In addition, the small water stream produced by enzymatic degradation of PET has been selected for treatment, due to the high value compounds that can be recovered.

For each of the three processes, membrane-based solutions have been proposed and, in some cases, already tested. For the plastic washing wastewater, ultrafiltration was selected to remove the solids from the water. This also makes sure microplastics are removed, so they are prevented from ending up in the environment.

For the enzymatic degradation broth, ultrafiltration with a specific molecular weight cutoff of 10kDa was used, so the monomers could be separated from the enzymes and leftover plastics. This ensured monomer recovery of about 90%.

For the recovery of salt from the supernatant of PHBV recovery, electrodialysis is the most suitable technology. Electrodialysis selectively removes salt from the water stream, whereas the organic compounds that could influence PHBV production stay behind. The salts can be reintroduced in the fermentation broth, and the organic waste stream can be either discarded or reused in a different process.

During WP6-demonstrators, these three technological solutions will be tested on prepilot or pilot scale to evaluate their suitability on large scale in a production line. During this testing stage, the energy requirements of the technologies will be evaluated, and used in the energy recommendation of the project.

5 References

- [1] THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL, “DIRECTIVE 2012/27/EU - Energy efficiency,” 2012.
- [2] AChEE, “Guía para la calificación de consultores en eficiencia energética,” 2015.
- [3] J. Cox, C. Hallock, E. Hotchkiss, A. Kandt and K. Kiatreungwattana, “Nurseries Best Practices Guide for Energy and Water Efficiency, Renewable Energy, and Resilience,” 2021.
- [4] G. Erbach, “Understanding energy efficiency,” 2015.
- [5] The European Parliament and of the Council, “Directive 2010/31/EU - Energy performance of buildings,” 2010.
- [6] C. Nocito and V. Koncar, “18 - Flexible photovoltaic cells embedded into textile structures,” in *Smart Textiles and their Applications*, WP, 2016, pp. 401 - 422.
- [7] EIA, “Biomass explained,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.eia.gov/energyexplained/biomass/>.
- [8] K. Bracmort, “Biomass: Comparison of Definitions in Legislation,” 2013.
- [9] A. Gardel, *Energy Economy and Prospective: A Handbook for Engineers and Economists*, Pergamon Press, 1981.
- [10] S. Bhatia, “4 - Solar thermal energy,” in *Advanced Renewable Energy Systems*, WPI, 2014, pp. 94 - 143.
- [11] IEA, “An introduction to biogas and biomethane,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/outlook-for-biogas-and-biomethane-prospects-for-organic-growth/an-introduction-to-biogas-and-biomethane>.
- [12] EIA, “Hydrogen explained,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.eia.gov/energyexplained/hydrogen/#:~:text=Hydrogen%20is%20the%20simplest%20element,of%20hydrogen%20and%20helium%20gases>.

- [13] J. Sevillano, “Precipitaciones anuales y mensuales en ciudades españolas y europeas y otros datos climáticos,” Agosto 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://clima.javiersevillano.es/PrecipitacionMediaAnual.htm>.
- [14] X. D. Ramírez, “Desalinización: Objetivo, bajar de los 2,9 kWh/m³,” 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iagua.es/blogs/xavi-duran-ramirez/desalinizacion-objetivo-bajar-29-kwhm3>.
- [15] REN21, “Renewables 2021 Global Status Report,” Paris, 2021.
- [16] I. Ghosh, “A Global Breakdown of Greenhouse Gas Emissions by Sector,” 2020.
- [17] University of Calgaray, “Energy Education - energy transformations,” University of Calgaray, 2020. [Online]. Available: https://energyeducation.ca/encyclopedia/Energy_transformations.
- [18] S. Giaccone, “Energy efficiency measurement in industrial processes,” 2011.
- [19] AleaSoft, “The transport decarbonisation challenge on the eve of a new era without emissions,” 19 May 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://aleasoft.com/transport-decarbonisation-challenge-eve-new-era-without-emissions/>.
- [20] M. Puri, “Chilling Prospects 2022: Promoting sustainable agricultural food chains through the Energy Smart Food programme,” 3 June 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.seforall.org/data-stories/promoting-sustainable-agricultural-food-chains>.
- [21] Food and Agriculture Organization, “Chapter 2: Energy for Agriculture,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.fao.org/3/x8054e/x8054e05.htm#:~:text=2.4%20Agricultural%20Energy%20Needs&text=The%20direct%20energy%20needs%20include,of%20agricultural%20inputs%20and%20outputs..>
- [22] Carbon trust, “Energy efficiency in agriculture. Sector guide”.
- [23] K. Ragazou, A. Garefalakis, E. Zafeiriou and I. Passas, “Agriculture 5.0: A New Strategic Management Mode for a Cut Cost and an Energy Efficient Agriculture Sector,” *Energies*, 2022.
- [24] S. C. G. S. N. Weinert, “Methodology for planning and operating energy-efficient production systems,” 2011.

- [25] M. J.-K. & P. Drozyner, “The Role of Maintenance in Reducing the Negative Impact of a Business on the Environment,” 2016.
- [26] C. Altmann, “Reliabilityweb,” [Online]. Available: <https://reliabilityweb.com/sp/articles/entry/el-mantenimiento-y-la-eficiencia-energetica..>
- [27] Agencia Andaluza de la Energía, “Metodología para la elaboración de auditorías energéticas en la industria,” Sevilla, 2011.
- [28] Engineering ToolBox, “Engineering ToolBox, 2003,” [Online]. Available: https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/boiler-combustion-efficiency-d_271.html.
- [29] Thermal, “Thermal,” [Online]. Available: http://www.thermal.cl/docs/articulos_tecnicos/articulo___economizadores.pdf.
- [30] Vapormat Saacke, “Vapormat Saacke,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.vapormat-saacke.com/perdidas-de-energia-en-calderas>.
- [31] ABB, “ABB,” [Online]. Available: <https://new.abb.com/drives/es/que-es-un-variador>.
- [32] Fricorredor, “Fricorredor,” [Online]. Available: http://www.fricorredor.com/pdf/condensacion_flotante.pdf.
- [33] SEGUAS, “Seguas - Aire comprimido industrial,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.seguas.com/eficiencia-energetica-fugas-aire-comprimido/>.
- [34] AEC, “AEC,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.aec.es/web/guest/centro-conocimiento/sistemas-de-gestion-energetica>.
- [35] OMRON, “OMRON,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.infopl.net/noticias/item/101504-variadores-de-velocidad-omron-ahorrar-energia-para-reducir-costes-y-mejorar-la-competitividad>.
- [36] AEC, “AEC,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.aec.es/web/guest/centro-conocimiento/sistemas-de-gestion-energetica>.
- [37] J. Tsui, “Predictions and trends for the energy sector in 2020,” 2020.
- [38] Enhar Sustainable Energy Solutions, “NSW Small Wind Turbine Consumer Guide,” 2010.
- [39] World Nuclear Association, “Renewable Energy And Electricity,” 2020.

- [40] O. Planas, “Solar Energy Technology 2020,” [Online]. Available: <https://solar-energy.technology/solar-thermal>.
- [41] X. L. H. L. L. Z. R. Zhang, “Analysis of a feasible trigeneration system taking solar energy and biomass as co-feeds,” 2016.
- [42] E. Folk, “How Solar and Wind Energy Are Now Cheaper than Fossil Fuels,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.altenergymag.com/article/2020/05/how-solar-and-wind-energy-are-now-cheaper-than-fossil-fuels/33132>.
- [43] International Renewable Energy Agency, “Future of Wind: Deployment, investment, technology, grid integration and socio-economic aspects,” IRENA, 2019.
- [44] International Energy Agency, [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/fuels-and-technologies/hydrogen>.
- [45] Y. Majeed, M. U. Khan, M. Waseem, U. Zahid, F. Mahmood, F. Majeed, M. Sultan and A. Raza, “Renewable energy as an alternative source for energy management in agriculture,” *Energy Reports*, pp. 344 - 359, 2023.
- [46] Y. d. J. Acosta-Silva, I. Torres-Pacheco, Y. Matsumoto, M. Toledano-Ayala, G. M. Soto-Zarazúa, O. Zelaya-Ángel and A. Méndez-López, “Applications of solar and wind renewable energy in agriculture: A review,” *Science Progress*, vol. 102, no. 2, pp. 127 - 140, 2019.
- [47] Energypedia, “Hydropower in Powering Agriculture,” [Online]. Available: https://energypedia.info/wiki/Hydropower_in_Powering_Agriculture.
- [48] Z. Guo, Y. Sun, S.-Y. Pan and P.-C. Chiang, “Integration of Green Energy and Advanced Energy-Efficient Technologies for Municipal Wastewater Treatment Plants,” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 16, no. 7, 2019.
- [49] C. Agaton, C. Guno, R. Villanueva and R. Villanueva, “Optimal investment schemes for residential solar photovoltaic project in the Philippines,” *Applied Energy Symposium 2019: Low carbon cities and urban energy systems*, Xiamen, 2019.
- [50] Energías Renovables, “El periodo medio de amortización de una instalación fotovoltaica es hoy de 5 años,” *Energías Renovables*, 15 Enero 2016.

- [51] Refacsol, “¿Cuál es el tiempo de vida promedio de un Panel Solar?,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://refacsol.com/cual-es-el-tiempo-de-vida-promedio-de-un-panel-solar/#:~:text=Es%20por%20ello%2C%20que%20en,de%2020%20a%2025%20a%C3%B1os..>
- [52] International Renewable Energy Agency, “Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2019,” UAE, Abu Dhabi, 2020.
- [53] N. H. H. Tra, U. Safder, X. Q. N. Nguyen and C. Yoo, “Multi-objective decision-making and optimal sizing of a hybrid renewable energy system to meet the dynamic energy demands of a wastewater treatment plant,” *Energy*, vol. 191, 2020.
- [54] BBVA, “¿Qué es el biogás, cómo se obtiene y para qué se utiliza?,” BBVA, [Online]. Available: <https://www.bbva.com/es/sostenibilidad/que-es-el-biogas-como-se-obtiene-y-para-que-se-utiliza>.
- [55] OECD, “Managing water sustainably is key to the future of food and agriculture,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.oecd.org/agriculture/topics/water-and-agriculture/>.
- [56] A. Zimmer, “New water uses in the Segura basin: conflicts around gated communities in Murcia,” *Water International*, vol. 35, no. 1, 2010.
- [57] European Parliament, “Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse (Text with EEA relevance),” 2020.
- [58] J. Hristov, J. Barreiro-Hurle, G. Salputra, M. Blanco and P. Witzke, “Reuse of treated water in European agriculture: Potential to address water scarcity under climate change,” *Agricultural Water Management*, 31 May 2021.
- [59] N. Voulvoulis, “Water reuse from a circular economy perspective and potential risks from an unregulated approach,” *Current Opinion in Environmental Science & Health*, vol. 2, pp. 32 - 45, 2018.
- [60] European Council, “Decision No. 1386/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 November 2013 on a General Union Environment Action Programme to 2020 ‘Living well, within the limits of our planet’ (L 354/171),” 2013.

- [61] United Nations, “Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development,” New York, 2015.
- [62] European Council, “Council Directive 98/83/EC of 3 November 1998 on the quality of water intended for human consumption (Drinking Water Directive) (98/83/EC),” 1998.
- [63] European Council, “Council Directive 91/271/EEC concerning urban waste-water treatment (91/271/EEC),” 1991.
- [64] European Council, “Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for community action in the field of water policy (EU Water Framework Directive—WFD) (2000/60/EC),” 2000.
- [65] M. Smol, C. Adam and M. Preisner, “Circular economy model framework in the European water and wastewater sector,” *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, vol. 22, pp. 682-697, 2020..
- [66] A. Amobonye, P. Bhagwat, S. Raveendran, S. Singh and S. Pillai, “Environmental Impacts of Microplastics and Nanoplastics: A Current Overview,” *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 15 December 2021.
- [67] L. Huisman, “Sedimentation and flotation,” [Online]. Available: https://ocw.tudelft.nl/wp-content/uploads/Sedimentation_and_flotation_TU2004.pdf..
- [68] K. Rajala, O. Grönfors, M. Hesampour and A. Mikola, “Removal of microplastics from secondary wastewater treatment plant effluent by coagulation/flocculation with iron, aluminum and polyamine-based chemicals,” *Water Research*, vol. 183, 2020.
- [69] J. Dickhout, J. M. P. Biesheuvel, L. Boels, R. Lammertink and W. d. Vos, “Produced water treatment by membranes: A review from a colloidal perspective,” *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, vol. 487, pp. 523 - 534, 2017.
- [70] Pentair, “Membrane Technology,” [Online]. Available: <https://xflow.pentair.com/en/spectrum/membrane-technology-in-general>.
- [71] “Electrodialysis,” [Online]. Available: <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=8768907>.
- [72] M. Tomaszewska, “Air Gap Membrane Distillation (AGMD),” *Encyclopedia of Membranes*, pp. 33 - 34, 2016.

A2C – Deliverable D1.7 v2.0

[73] “SiccaDania-hydrocyclone.png,” [Online]. Available:
<https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=107733158>.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.